

Master's Thesis

AgriGenomics

Regulation of CHS during the cross-talk between
UV-B and MAMP triggered immunity

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List of Abbreviations

4CL: 4-coumaroyl CoA

ABA: Abscisic acid

ABFs: ABA response element-binding factors

ABRE: ABA-responsive promoter elements

ACC: 1-Aminocyclopropane-1-Carboxylic Acid

ACT2: ACTIN 2

ash1: absent, small or homeotic discs 1

ASHH2: Arabidopsis ASH1 HOMOLOG 2

ATX1: Arabidopsis Trithorax-1 Methyltransferase

At: *Arabidopsis thaliana*

Avr: Avirulence

BAK1: BRI1-associated Receptor Kinase

BIK1: Botrytis-induced Kinase 1

bZIP: basic leucine Zipper

C4H: Cinnamate 4-Hydroxylase

cDNA: Complementary DNA

CDPK: Calcium-Dependent Protein Kinases

CHI: Chalcone Flavanone Isomerase

CHS: Chalcone Synthase

Col-0: Columbia ecotype

DEPC: Diethylpyrocarbonate

DNA: Deoxyribonucleic Acid

dNTP: Deoxynucleotide

ECD: Extracellular Domain

EDTA: Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid

List of Abbreviations

EF-Tu: Elongation Factor-Tu

ET: Enhancer Trap

ETI: Effector-Triggered Immunity

F/U: flg22+UV-B

F3H: Flavanone 3-Hydroxylase

FLS2: FLAGELLIN SENSING 2

FPGs: Flavonol Pathway genes

FRK1: Flg22-induced Receptor-like Kinase 1

GEF: Guanine Nucleotide Exchange Factor

GFP: Green Fluorescent Protein

GST1: Glutathione S-Transferase 1

H3K9ac: H3 lysine 9 acetylation

HATs: Histone Acetyltransferases

HDACs: Histone Deacetylases

HPLC: High-performance Liquid Chromatography

HY5: ELONGATED HYPOCOTYL 5

ICD: Intracellular Domain

JA: Jasmonic Acid

LPS: Lipopolysaccharides

LRR-RK: Leucin-rich Repeat Receptor Kinase

MAMPs/PAMPs: Microbe/Pathogen-associated Molecular Pattern

MAPK/MPK: Mitogen activated protein kinase

MEKK/MAP3K/MAPKKK/: Mitogen activated protein kinase kinase kinase

MKK/MEK/MAP2K: Mitogen activated protein kinase kinase

MKS1: Meckel Syndrome Type 1

NADPH: Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide Phosphate

List of Abbreviations

NB-LRR: Nucleotide binding-Leucin Rich Repeat

NaCl: Natrium Chloride

PAL1: Phenylalanine Ammonia-Lyase 1

PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction

PFG: PRODUCTION OF FLAVONOL GLYCOSIDES

PGNs: Peptidoglycans

PP2C: Protein Phosphatase 2C

PR1: Pathogenesis-Related Protein 1

PR5: Pathogenesis-Related Protein 5

PRRs: Pattern Recognition Receptors

PTI: PAMP Triggered Immunity

PYR/PYLs: PYRABACTIN RESISTANCE 1/PYR

RBOHD: Respiratory Burst Oxidase-D

RCC1: Regulator of Chromatin Condensation 1

RLKs: Receptor-like Kinases

RLPs: Receptor-like Proteins

RNA: Ribonucleic Acid

ROS: Reactive Oxygen Species

SAR: Systemic Acquired Resistance

SDS: Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate

SERK: Somatic-Embryogenesis Receptor-like Kinase

SPA1: Supressor of PHY A-105 1

SnRK2s: Sucrose Nonfermenting (SNF)-related Kinase

T-DNA: Transfer DNA

TE buffer: Tris-EDTA buffer

List of Abbreviations

TF: Transcription Factor

THI2.1: THIONIN2.1

Tris: Tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane

UV: Ultraviolet

UVR8: UV RESISTANCE LOCUS 8

WT: Wild Type

Zm: *Zea mays*

1) Introduction

1.1 General Introduction to Plant-Environment interactions

Because of their sessile lifestyle, in the field plants are exposed to constant stress factors of both biotic and abiotic nature. The main types of abiotic stress include heat, cold, salinity, drought, frost, high light intensity and nutrient deficiency. On the other hand herbivores and pathogens like bacteria, fungi, viruses and nematodes are inflicting the biotic stress. In natural conditions, it is often the case that plants need to deal with more than one stress type at the same time. The response of plants to such stress combinations is unique and cannot be directly extrapolated from their response to each of the different stresses applied individually (Suzuki et al.,2014). Now plants have to use different, sometimes opposite signaling pathways at the same time in order to handle the simultaneous threats, which results in an even higher degree of complexity in stress responses (Suzuki et al.,2014).

Figure 1, modified after Suzuki et al. (2014). The effects of drought, heat stress, and their combination on the growth and development of wheat /maize entire plants and their reproductive organs. In flowers drought impairs pistil, and heat impairs pollen development. Common symptoms of drought stress on the entire plant include reduced height, spike number, and grain weight. On the other hand, heat stress lowers the overall number of grains, and increases the number of aborted spikes. Different individual effects of drought and heat stack up and impact plants simultaneously when combined.

Metabolic and signaling pathways involved in plant response to stress combinations were found to include transcription factors (TFs), photosynthesis, hormone signaling and osmolyte synthesis, but majority of mechanisms used by the plant to respond to the stress combinations still remain unclear.

1.2 Plant response to biotic stress factors

1.2.1 General recognition mechanisms

In their habitat, plants are always surrounded by a vast array of microorganisms. Plant-microbe communication takes part in both phyllosphere and rhizosphere of plants. Within this interaction microbes have a dualistic role. They can be beneficial or pathogenic to their plant host. In order to establish a pathosystem with plants, microbes have evolved a deadly array of weapons. And yet we see healthy plants in our surroundings. How can that be the case when the attacks are coming from all sides, at all times? This is due to the fact that plants possess constitutive defense mechanisms, e.g. for physical restriction (cuticle layer, waxy epidermis, and the rigid cell wall) or chemical inhibition of the pathogen (antimicrobial secondary metabolites). Most potential pathogens fail to break these preformed barriers, so the colonization of the host doesn't take place. This non-host resistance is the most common type of disease resistance shown by the entire plant species against all isolates of a pathogenic microbial species. (Senthil-Kumar et al.,2013; Cook et al.,2015; Fan et al.,2012; Uma et al.,2011; Kirankumar,2004).

However, if a pathogen manages to overcome the constitutive defense mechanisms by entering through natural openings (stomata and hydathodes) or wounds, it will be recognized by the plant cell and induce a plant defense reaction, called basal defense. This recognition occurs in response to attacks by both host or non-host pathogens (Zipfel et al.,2004). Plants use trans-membrane pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) to detect evolutionary conserved components of microbe/pathogen-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs/PAMPs). The recognition of MAMPs/PAMPs by plant PRRs leads to PAMP-triggered immunity (PTI) - a first line of defense against most non-adapted pathogens. Some features of PTI include calcium fluxes and bursts of reactive oxygen species (ROS), callose deposition, activation of mitogen-associated and calcium-dependent protein kinases (MAPKs and CDPKs) leading to massive transcriptional reprogramming, and generation of second messengers (Jones and Dangl,2006; Greff et al.,2012; Monaghan and Zipfel,2012).

In plants, the most studied PRRs are receptor-like kinases (RLKs) and the receptor like proteins (RLPs). The plant RLK family counts more than 600 members in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, but only for a small number of them a role in MAMP recognition has been demonstrated (Pel and Pieterse,2012). RLKs are surface localized, transmembrane receptors with extracellular ligand recognition domain and an intracellular kinase domain involved in signal transduction. They can recognize distinct ligands of a microbial origin or ligands derived from intracellular protein/carbohydrate signals. RLPs have a similar structure, but lack the intracellular kinase domain (Greff et al.,2012). MAMP recognizing RLKs combined with other proteins that might function in MAMP detection offer a high number of putative receptors for plants. However, the number of microbes from the environment possibly encountered is almost unlimited, so plants need to recognize structures that are common in large groups of micro-organisms (common MAMPs) in order

to stay competitive. Well known examples of these common MAMPs are prokaryotic elongation factor-Tu (EF-Tu), flagellin, lipopolysaccharide (LPS) of Gram-negative bacteria, peptidoglycans (PGNs), chitin of fungal pathogens, glucans and glycoproteins from oomycetes (Pel and Pieterse,2012; Greff et al.,2012; Boller and Felix,2009).

The above mentioned MAMPs differ in their structure, origin and function in micro-organisms. However, they have a number of characteristics in common making them suitable ligands to be recognized by plant PRRs. They are widespread (e.g. chitin is spread through the fungal kingdom and all bacteria contain PGNs and EF-Tu) and are all highly conserved as well as essential, thus pathogens cannot change them in order to evade recognition (Pel and Pieterse,2012).

Figure 2, modified after Zipfel,2014. Plant pattern-recognition receptors (PRRs) are recognizing bacterial pathogens. In higher plants, the conserved leucine-rich repeat receptor kinase (LRR-RK) FLAGELLIN SENSING 2 (FL2) (red color) detects flagellin via the flg22 epitope. In *Solanaceae* family the flagellin derived epitope flgII-28 is detected via still unknown PRR. The bacterial elongation factor Tu (EF-Tu) is perceived via the LRR-RK EFR (blue) in *Brassicaceae* family, and the EF-Tu-derived epitope EFa50 is perceived in rice by still unknown PRR. The co-receptor LRR-RK BAK1 interacts with both FLS2 and EFR right after the binding of flg22 or elf18, respectively. Peptidoglycans (PGNs) bind to the Arabidopsis lysine motif receptor-like proteins (LysM-RLPs) LYM1 and LYM3, which may form a complex with the LysM-RK CERK1 on PGN recognition. In rice, PGNs bind to the LysM-RLPs LYP4 and LYP6. In rice, still unknown *Xanthomonas oryzae pv. oryzae* PAMP is detected by LRR-RK XA21 and XA3/26 which interact with LRR-RK Os CERK2 to confer the resistance against this pathogen. Also in Arabidopsis, LRR-RK ReMAX is detecting unknown MAMPs coming from xanthomonads, which are eliciting the defense responses in Arabidopsis, and some other *Brassicaceae*. Normal arrows indicate direct binding, and dashed arrows indicate lack of direct binding evidence, candidate PRR, or ligand.

Pathogens have evolved effectors to serve several roles including suppression of one or more components of PTI. On the other hand, plants can recognize them by specific disease resistance (R) genes which encode Nucleotide binding leucine rich repeat (NB-LRR) proteins. As the result of pathogen effector recognition (termed avirulence - Avr proteins when recognized) by a corresponding NB-LRR protein, Effector-Triggered Immunity (ETI) occurs. This type of plant-pathogen interaction puts both Avr and R-gene

encoded proteins under a diversifying selection, constituting a never-ending evolutionary arms race between these organisms (Jones and Dangl,2006).

Figure 3, modified after Felix and Boller,2009. Microbe-Associated Molecular Patterns (MAMPs), Damage-Associated Molecular Patterns (DAMPs), and pathogen effectors are detected by plant Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs) and R-gene encoded NB-LRR (nucleotide binding and leucine rich repeat domain) proteins, respectively. Plant cells sense them as danger signals, and triggers the defense response. During the evolution, pathogens develop new effectors as avirulence factors, and plants evolve new PRRs and resistance (R) proteins, leading to a never-ending evolutionary arms race between these organisms.

1.2.2 Flagellin/flg22 and flg22-signaling

Flagellin is the major structural protein of eubacterial flagella (Zipfel et al.,2004). Bacterial motility, which allows bacteria to respond to favorable or unfavorable stimuli in their environment, is based on the flagellum (Moens,1996). Apart from motility, flagella participate in many additional processes in bacteria including adhesion, biofilm formation, virulence factor secretion, and modulation of the immune system of eukaryotic cells (Duan et al.,2011). Flagellin has a filament structure with highly conserved N and C termini, while

the central region is characterized by a very high variability (Felix and Boller,1999).

The perception of flagellin in plants was discovered after treating cell cultures of tomato with boiled *P. syringae* pv. *tabaci* bacteria as crude elicitor. Various defense responses were the result of the highly sensitive recognition of a conserved N-terminal domain of flagellin by the plant PRR leucine-rich repeat (LRR) receptor kinase FLAGELLIN SENSING 2 (FLS2). It has been discovered that the elicitor-active synthetic peptide, a 22 amino acids large epitope flg22, from the conserved region, was alone more potent than the purified flagellin (Pel and Pieterse,2012; Felix and Boller,1999).

Furthermore, it has been shown that synthetic peptide flg22 can also elicit the *Arabidopsis thaliana* defense response (Gomez-Gomez et al.,1999). Some of the plant reactions upon treatment with flg22 include oxidative burst, callose deposition, ethylene production, growth inhibition of seedlings, hypersensitive response, production of defense related compounds such as phytoalexins (camalexin and scopoletin) as well as cell wall strengthener lignin - a structural barrier that restricts pathogen spread, and up-regulation of defense genes like PR1, PR5, PAL1 and GST1 (Gomez-Gomez and Boller,2002; Nicaise et al.,2009; Schenke et al.,2011).

Gomez-Gomez and Boller (2000) have reported that the FLS2 locus encoding for the RLK is the PRR for the PAMP flg22. Like every other known plant PRR which belongs to the RLK family, FLS2 is also localized in the plasma membrane and contains an extracellular domain (ECD), a single-pass transmembrane (TM) domain, and intracellular domain (ICD). Its ECD contains 28 LLRs, and its intracellular kinase domain is serine/threonine specific (Newman et al.,2013). Initiation of PTI is a rather complex process that involves genes other than FLS2 alone. Chinchilla et al. (2007) reported that FLS2 interacts with BAK1 (BRI1-associated receptor kinase), a LRR-RLKs which regulates the brassinosteroid receptor BRI1, and acts as the positive regulator in this signaling. Roux et al. (2011) observed a ligand-induced heteromerization between FLS2 and LRR-RLKs of somatic-embryogenesis receptor-like kinase (SERK) family (including BAK1), which appears to be generally required for the MAMP induced plant responses. BIK1 (Botrytis-induced kinase1) is found to contribute to this interaction as well. It becomes rapidly phosphorylated upon flagellin precipitation, to further dissociate from the FLS2-BAK1 complex and serve as a link between the MAMP receptors and downstream intracellular signaling (Lu et al.,2009). This is accompanied by the bursts of Ca^{2+} activating the *At* NADPH oxidase RbohD, which contributes to the generation of ROS in response to pathogen attack and Ca^{2+} dependent protein kinases (CDPKs) (Ranf et al.,2011). Involvement of mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling in flg22 downstream signaling has already been reported (concretely MAP3K–MKK4/MKK5 MPK3/MPK6 and MEKK1–MKK1/MKK2–MPK4) (Asai et al.,2002; Suarez Rodriguez et al.,2010; Segonzac and Zipfel,2011), however, no direct link to the above mentioned interaction can be drawn. Some WRKY TFs could be directly associated with MAPK signaling. An example for it includes the interaction between MPK4 and VQ domain containing protein MKS1 (Andreasson et al.,2005). Anyhow, it is found that VQ motif containing proteins can usually recognize the WRKY TFs (Lai et al.,2011; Cheng et al.,2012), which will be activated to take up the role in the regulation of plant stress responsive genes (Rushton et al.,2010; Ishihama and Yoshioka,2012). Interestingly, some WRKYs like AtWRKY 38 and AtWRKY62 have been found to interact with HDAC19 as negative regulators of basal defense, and might therefore also affect histone acetylation (Kim et al.,2008).

1.3 Plant response to abiotic stress

1.3.1 General recognition mechanisms

Abscisic acid (ABA) is one of the most important phytohormones serving as an endogenous messenger in both biotic and abiotic stress responses and a regulator of many key processes in plants (Chan,2012; Hirayama and Shinozaki,2007). Drought and salinity were found to influence the expression of ABA-related genes and strongly increase the levels of ABA in stressed plants (Chan et al.,2012; Rabbani et al.,2003). Perception of ABA through four types of receptors has been reported (Gonzalez_Guzman et al.,2012). One of them is family of START domain proteins known as PYRABACTIN RESISTANCE 1/PYR like PYR/PYLs. Several PYR/PYLs interact with and inhibit six out of nine Arabidopsis clade A PP2C (protein phosphatase 2C) genes (Santiago et al.,2009). On the other hand, SnRK2s (sucrose non-fermenting (SNF)-related kinase) was found to play a role of a positive regulator of ABA signaling (Yoshida et al.,2002). Active, autophosphorylated SnRK2 is kept inactive by PP2Cs through physical interaction and dephosphorylation. After binding ABA, PYR/PYLs associate with PP2Cs and inhibit them, preventing PP2C-mediated dephosphorylation of SnRK2 (Park et al.,2009). Once accumulated, phosphorylated SnRK2s lead to subsequent phosphorylation of bZIP (basic leucine zipper) transcription factors ABFs (ABA response element-binding factors) (Johnson et al.,2002; Furihata et al.,2005). ABFs will further bind to ABA-responsive promoter elements (ABRE), and induce the expression of ABA-responsive genes (Zhu,2002). Since a GENEVESTIGATOR analysis showed that MYB12 and its flavonol pathway targets are down-regulated in *aba1-1* and *abi1-1* mutants (vs *Ler-0* wild type), an involvement of ABA in this context is also possible (Schenke et al.,2011). This is further supported by findings in maize, where it was shown that UV-B treatment increased ABA levels and ABA-mutants were more susceptible to UV-B radiation than the wild type (Tossi et al.,2009 and 2012) or in grape, where ABA contributes to UV-B protection (Berli et al.,2010).

1.3.2 UV-B induced responses and signaling

Ultraviolet (UV) radiation is the portion of the electromagnetic spectrum between X-rays (0.01-10 nm) and visible light (400-700 nm). UV-B light is conventionally divided into UV-A (315 to 400 nm), UV-B (280 to 315 nm) and UV-C (100 to 280 nm) radiation. UV-C is entirely absorbed by the ozone layer, and UV-A and some UV-B radiation are reaching the Earth's surface. UV-B is the most harmful form of radiation, because it can cause photochemical DNA damage (Ulm and Jenkis,2015).

All organisms have the same chemical structure of DNA, hence share similar susceptibility to UV-B light. However, plants depend on the sunlight for the photosynthesis, so the balance between optimal light capture and UV-B protection needs to be found. Many crops are grown over the summertime on the open fields and yet manage not to get sunburned. This is due to the fact that plants possess a combination of protective and repair mechanisms against UV-B light, for example they can accumulate the UV-B-absorbing sunscreen metabolites in the vacuoles of epidermal cells, increase the levels of antioxidants, protect the photosynthetic apparatus, and increase the levels of DNA repair enzymes (Ulm and Jenkis,2015).

Plants also produce UV-protective secondary metabolites. Flavonoids, for example, are secondary metabolites involved in several aspects of plant development and defense

(Hichri et al.,2010). Along with other phenylpropanoids, they are synthesized from phenylalanine. The biosynthesis process involves activity of three enzymes (phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL), cinnamate 4-hydroxylase (C4H) and 4-coumaroyl CoA ligase (4CL)), to generate p coumaroyl CoA - active intermediate for the various branches of phenylpropanoid metabolism (Zhang et al.,2015).

Figure 4, modified after Zhang et al.,2015. The schematic representation of plant phenylpropanoid pathway. PAL (phenylalanine ammonia lyase); C4H (cinnamate 4 hydroxylase); 4CL (4-coumaroyl CoA ligase).

Regulation of this biosynthetic pathway is largely transcriptional and controlled by a network of TFs, among which the PRODUCTION OF FLAVONOL GLYCOSIDES (PFG) family of R2R3-MYB transcription factors was identified with a pivotal function. The MYB family of proteins is large, functionally diverse and represented in all eukaryotes. MYB proteins are key factors in regulatory networks controlling development, metabolism and responses to biotic and abiotic stresses (Dubos et al.,2010). In Arabidopsis seedlings, three functionally redundant MYB TFs, AtMYB11, AtMYB12 and AtMYB111, regulate flavonol branch of flavonoid pathway by activating the transcription of following genes: Chalcone synthase (CHS), Chalcone Flavanone Isomerase (CHI), Flavanone 3-Hydroxylase (F3H), FLS35 (Pandey et al.,2015; Stracke et al.,2010). Also they act in an additive manner due to their differential spatial activity, whereby MYB12 controls flavonol biosynthesis mainly in the roots, while MYB111 controls flavonol biosynthesis primarily in cotyledons (Stracke et al.,2007).

Light perception in *Arabidopsis* involves different photoreceptors which cover the large part of light visible spectrum. These photoreceptors belong to different gene families, but the latest understanding of UV-B perception, signal transduction and downstream response came with the discovery and characterization of a seven-bladed propeller protein UV RESISTANCE LOCUS 8 (UVR8) (Ulm and Jenkis, 2015). The UV-B receptor UVR8 is a homodimer, but the absorption of UV-B induces its monomerisation. Monomers initiate a signaling cascade leading to a change in transcriptional regulation of genes responsible for plant survival in sunlight (Rizzini, 2011). Studies with transgenic plants expressing UVR8 fused to green fluorescent protein (GFP) showed its localization in cytoplasm and nucleus (Brown et al., 2005). However, UVR8 seems to be mainly active in the nucleus of plant cells, despite being abundant in the cytoplasm as well, which is shown by (Kaiserli and Jenkis, 2007). They conclude that UV-B promotes rapid (within minutes) accumulation of UVR8 in the nucleus via nuclear translocation. By overexpressing the UVR8 protein in *Arabidopsis*, Favory et al. (2009) showed an increase in UV-B photomorphogenesis, acclimation and tolerance to UV-B stress. Acclimation and tolerance to UV-B includes for example an increase in expression of antioxidant genes (regulation of glutathione pathways, phenylpropanoids, cinnamates, flavonoids, and pyridoxine biosynthesis pathways), and biosynthesis and accumulation of "sunscreen" pigments and DNA-repair enzymes. Acclimated plants do not show visible negative effects which disrupt cellular activities. Opposite to that, UV-B stressed plants suffer from the cellular damage that can't be coped with (Hildeg et al., 2013). Moreover, possible UVR8 orthologs can be identified in all plants where sequence information is available, indicating that UVR8 signaling is an evolutionarily ancient mechanism, consistent with a role in UV-protection of photosynthetic organisms (Ulm and Jenkis, 2015). In the nucleus UVR8 monomers interact with E3 ubiquitin ligase COP1 (Kaiserli and Jenkis, 2007; Jenkis, 2014). This UVR8-COP1 complex formation also involves SPA1 (Suppressor of PHY A-105 1). Its exact role still remains unclear, however the UVR8-COP1-SPA protein complex acts to positively regulate the photomorphogenic UV-B responses.

Figure 5, modified after Jenkis, 2014. UVR8 dimers are receiving UV-B light. This initiates monomerisation of UVR8, a conformational change, that allows UVR8 to later be associated with COP1 (E3 ubiquitin ligase component) and SPA1 (Suppressor of PHY A-105 1). UVR8-COP1-SPA complex initiates a signaling cascade, activating some light responsive target genes (like flavonol pathway genes). Among them, RUP (REPRESSOR OF UV-B PHOTOMORPHOGENESIS) proteins are activated. They will remove and substitute COP1-SPA complex, initiating the dimerisation of UVR8 once again.

The UVR8-COP1 complex stabilizes bZIP TF ELONGATED HYPOCOTYL 5 (HY5) by preventing its degradation. HY5 as a master regulator of UV-B photomorphogenic responses influences then the expression of UV-B related genes and the expression of HY5 itself (Heijde et al.,2013; Jenkis,2014; Jenkis,2009). A T/G-box cis -regulatory element within the HY5 promoter functions as an HY5 binding site and is essential for UV-B-induced HY5 expression (Abbas et al.,2014). In addition TF MYB12 was shown to act as a positive regulator in the expression of Flavonol Pathway genes (FPGs) during the crosstalk between UV-B (up-regulation of FPGs) and MAMP flg22 (down-regulation of FPGs) signaling (Schenke et al.,2011). HY5 targets the MYB12 promoter by binding to the ACE/G-box (CACGTG) (Lee et al.,2007; Stracke et al.,2010). MYB12 follows by binding itself to MYB-recognition element (MRE-box) [ACC(T/A)A(C/A)C] within the FPGs promoters (Mehrtens,2005), and together, in a tandem with HY5 activates the FPGs (Schenke et al.,2011). Promoter analysis have shown that MYB12 can also activate the expression of an another MYB TF - MYB4, which in turn down-regulates both MYB12 and itself, and has an overall negative impact on the expression of FPGs (Schenke et al.,2011). To further understand the regulation of these genes, changes in posttranslational histone modifications during the crosstalk between UV-B and MAMP signaling were observed at FPGs (CHS, CFI, and F3H), and MYB12 genomic loci. H3K9 acetylation at both promoter and open reading frame was induced by the UV-B light and suppressed by the concomitant treatment with flg22 (Schenke et al.,2014). H3K9 acetylation was increased at the HY5 locus after the plants were transferred from dark to light conditions, and decreased at some light-regulated loci in the *hy5-215* mutant (Guo et al.,2008). Therefore it might be concluded that HY5 and/or its downstream target MYB12 play an important role in H3K9 acetylation. Also it is tempting to assume that MYB TFs can indeed interact with histone acetyltransferases (HATs) or histone deacetylases (HDACs) (Schenke et al.,2014). It was also speculated that UVR8 might be able to influence the chromatin state (Tilbrook et al.,2013). It has sequence and structural similarity with human RCC1 (Regulator of Chromatin Condensation 1) - a already known chromatin-associated protein (Kliebenstein et al. 2002) which binds chromatin via histones and acts as a Guanine Nucleotide Exchange Factor (GEF) for GTPases (Binkert et al.,2016). However, recent studies of Binkert et al. (2016) have denied these speculations and showed that UVR8 does not bind specifically to chromatin at target genes. Interestingly, UV-B signaling pathway regulating CHS gene expression involves calmodulin, protein phosphorylation, and calcium ions which are not flowing in from across the plasma membrane, but rather derived from an intracellular calcium pool (Jenkis,2009). PTI and UV-B stress signaling can share two common players - MPK3 and MPK6, since UV-B light can induce signaling pathways in plants other than UVR8, like the one depending on MAP kinase (MPK) phosphatase 1 (Gonzalez Besteiro et al.,2011; Asai et al.,2002). Serving as a prerequisite in gene activation, both calcium and kinase activity can have a direct impact on the HY5 or activity of any other TF (González-Fontes et al.,2013), but also on the chromatin structure and DNA conformation as described in animal systems (Dobi et al.,1998; Mellström et al.,2008). This means that parallel induced signaling pathway is required to activate some genes (for example TFs binding to their corresponding cis responsive elements), in addition to making chromatin accessible for transcription.

1.4 Signaling cross-talk between biotic-abiotic stress induced plant responses

1.4.1 General introduction

The combined effect of different stress combinations on the yield, growth and physiology of plants can be negative or positive (Suzuki et al.,2014).

Some of the negative examples are the combination of drought and heat, causing an additive negative effect in plants, reducing the yield and the quality (Vile et al.,2012). Or the effect of salinity stress could be worse when combined with heat stress, primarily because plants with increased transpiration will end up taking up more salts (Keles and Öncel,2002). High light intensity could prove problematic to plants subjected to drought or cold stress. When exposed to drought or cold, plants inhibit their dark reactions because of low temperatures or unavailability of CO₂. On the other hand, strong light intensity results in high absorption of photosynthetic energy, which enhances oxygen reduction and thus ROS production (Suzuki et al.,2014; Giraud et al.,2008). Plants need energy and nutrients to acclimate in the environment. For example, micronutrients are essential for the activation of many ROS scavenging enzymes, hence (Mittler and Blumwald,2010) concluded that nutrient deficiency poses a serious problem when combined with any other stress. Srivastava et al. (2012) reported that combination of UV-B stress together with low as well as with high doses of Nickel have caused a growth inhibition in *Pisum sativum* L., accompanied by the decrease in chlorophyll content and photosynthetic activity via different mechanism which would not be triggered by any of these stresses individually. Negative interactions between biotic and abiotic stresses have also been addressed. For example (Szittyá et al.,2003) found that cold stress can impair gene silencing, a potent defense mechanism used by plants against viral pathogens.

Some stress combinations might have beneficial effects on plants, when compared with each of the individual stresses applied separately (Suzuki et al.,2014). In contrast to expected negative additive effect, the tomato plants exposed to salt and heat stress simultaneously were protected against salinity because these combined stresses induced the accumulation of glycine betaine and trehalose. Like that K⁺ concentration, along with cell wall status and photosynthesis was maintained, in contrast to reduction during the salinity stress only (Rivero et al.,2014). Also Ainsworth et al. (2008) consider elevated CO₂ concentrations beneficial when combined with other stresses, because higher CO₂ concentration decreases conductance of stomata, interferes with O₃ diffusion into leaves and improves water-use efficiency by decreasing transpiration.

It is known that plants trigger complex modes of integration of the different signaling pathways during stress combination. In those situations, the involvement of some novel mechanisms has also been reported (Suzuki et al.,2014). Rizhsky et al. (2002) found a large number of unique transcripts which are created during the combination of drought and heat stress in tobacco. None of them was produced upon exposing plants to each of them individually. Moreover, the response was followed up by accumulation of several unique metabolites and different proteins. Hewezi et al. (2008) had similar results in sunflower, observing the combined effect of heat and high light. Rasmussen et al.,2013 used microarray to study *Arabidopsis* transcriptome in response to combination of different biotic and abiotic factors. They found that some transcripts, mainly involved in Systemic Acquired Resistance (SAR), programmed cell death and salicylate biosynthesis had a similar response when different stress types were applied individually, and a different one to their combination. Transcripts regulating ethylene and auxin signaling in plant growth and the secondary metabolism like phenylpropanoids, responded differently to individual

different stress factors. However, when the combination of stresses comes at the same time, their expression receded back to control levels. Only a small amount of transcripts stayed the same when plants are challenged by the individual, and the stress combination. Prasch and Sonnewald (2013) using *Arabidopsis* under drought, heat stress and virus infection also concluded that the expression pattern of transcripts under stress combination cannot be predicted based on looking at each of the single stress conditions applied individually. Rather sometimes when both stress factors come simultaneously, priority needs to be set, and the more urgent threat will be dealt with first. Atkinson et al. (2013) purposed that plants are able to make these decisions, and based on them, prepare the defense mechanism. When *Arabidopsis* plants were subjected to drought, nematode infection, and their combination, majority of transcripts regulated by the stress combination were also regulated by drought alone, but not by nematode stress alone. This might point in the direction that drought was prioritized to nematode attack.

1.4.2 Cross-talk between UV-B and elicitor induced plant responses

It has already been known for two decades that MAMPs can down-regulate the UV-B stress-induced flavonol pathway. For instance this has been observed in parsley cell cultures or protoplasts treated with *Phytophthora sojae* crude elicitor (Dangl et al.,1987; Lozoya et al.,1991; Logemann and Hahlbrock,2002) or in carrot cell cultures treated with *Pythium aphanidermatum* crude elicitor (Gläßgen et al.,1998). Furthermore, onion and sorghum infected with *Botrytis allii* or *Cochliobolus heterostrophus* had reduced flavonoid and anthocyanin biosynthesis, respectively (Lo and Nicholson,1998; McLusky et al.,1999), indicating that this may be a common mechanism also functional in plants.

Schenke et al. (2011) observed a similar pattern in *Arabidopsis* Col-0 cell suspension cultures. UV-B light induced the production of flavonols - plant "sunscreen" secondary metabolites. Concomitantly, bacterial elicitor flg22 was applied, and the production of flavonols was suppressed. In parallel, flg22 treatment induced the production of defense-related compounds like lignin and phytoalexins (scopoletin). Since the substrate for the production of both flavonols and phytoalexins is coming from the same – phenylpropanoid pathway, it can be speculated that plant recognized the flg22 elicitation as a bigger threat, and on the expense of "sunscreen" production, focused its defense against pathogen. It appears that this crosstalk engaged two antagonistic MYB TFs - the main positive regulator MYB12 (Mehrtens et al.,2005; Stracke et al.,2010) and a negative feedback regulator MYB4 (Jin et al.,2000) of the flavonol and the general phenylpropanoid pathway, respectively. They were conversely regulated by both stresses: MYB12 expression was activated by UV-B and suppressed in the co-treatment with flg22, as were FPG transcripts. Additionally, MYB4 can be activated by both UV-B (in a feedback inhibitory manner via MYB12) and elicitation with flg22. However, MYB4 activation occurs much faster after flg22 treatment, indicating that MYB4 is high-jacked during the PTI to quickly down-regulate MYB12 and flavonol pathway structural genes. This allows shutting down production of ultraviolet UV-protective flavonol metabolites in favor of scopoletin and lignin (a barrier to hamper the spread of the pathogen by cell wall fortification) formation. These two antagonistic TFs MYB4 and MYB12 might play a crucial role in this cross-talk (Schenke et al.,2011).

1.5 Epigenetic modifications

1.5.1 General introduction to epigenetic

Epigenetics refers to heritable changes in patterns of gene expression that occur without alterations in the DNA sequence. Typically, epigenetic changes affect the chromatin structure. They involve covalent modifications of DNA and histones, which can furthermore be mediated at several interdependent levels including DNA methylation, histone post translational modifications and expression of histone variants (Chinnusamy et al.,2011). Since chromatin states can be propagated through mitotic and meiotic divisions, epigenetic mechanisms are thought to provide heritable "cellular memory", allowing plants to better cope with similar stress factors in the future (Iwasaki and Paszkowski,2014).

This may be especially true in plant systems with limited seed dispersal, leading to very similar environmental conditions for both parent and offspring. However, chromatin alterations are also reversible and often involved in simple gene-regulation without affecting the next generation (Eichten et al.,2014).

Chromatin structure plays an important role in the gene expression. It is of great importance because the physical structure of the DNA, as it exists packed into chromatin, can affect the ability of TFs and RNA polymerases to bind to specific genes and transcribe them (Pfluger and Wagner,2007). When chromatin is highly compacted (called heterochromatin), it is not available to factors involved in DNA transcription, replication and repair. On the other hand, once the chromatin decondenses and relaxes (called euchromatin), the active transcription takes place (Iwasaki and Paszkowski,2014).

Gene expression is regulated by altering these chromatin constraints in response to endogenous and exogenous cues, which ultimately creates a cell- or stimulus-specific accessible genome. Within the context of chromatin, three processes act together to regulate gene expression and thus should be considered together:

- 1) Histone modifications - histone modifiers covalently alter amino acids primarily in the exposed N terminal tails of histones, which changes the histone-DNA interaction and creates or blocks protein binding sites;
- 2) Chromatin remodeling - position or composition of nucleosomes is altered by chromatin remodeling ATPases with the energy derived from ATP hydrolysis;
- 3) DNA methylation - methylation of cytosine residues in the DNA interferes with binding of some proteins like TFs (Klose et al.,2006; Pfluger and Wagner, 2007). Some chromatin alterations and their impact on gene expression are summarized in Table 1 (Pfluger and Wagner,2007), and the dynamics of chromatin remodeling and histone modification in the context of epigenetic marks and ionic environment of the plant nucleus are shown in Figure 6.

Table 1: modified after Pfluger and Wagner (2007). Impact of chromatin remodeling on gene expression

Types of chromatin alterations that regulate gene expression				
Chromatin alteration ^a	Subtype	Acts upon	Mechanism	Outcome for transcription
Histone modifications	Ubiquitination	Lysine (K)	Distances histones from DNA (bulky moiety)	Activation (H2B) or repression (H2A) ^b
	Methylation	Lysine, arginine (R)	Recruitment of other chromatin regulators	Activation (H3K4, H3K36 ^c) or repression (H3K9 ^c , H3K27, H4K20, H4R3)
	Acetylation	Lysine	Charge neutralization ^d , recruitment of other chromatin regulators	Activation
	Phosphorylation	Serine (S), threonine (T)	Charge neutralization ^d , recruitment of other chromatin regulators	Activation
Chromatin ^e remodelling	SWI/SNF	Nucleosome position and occupancy	Sliding to new position, histone octamer eviction ^b	Activation and repression
	SWR1	Histone exchange	H2A.Z histone variant incorporation	Activation
DNA methylation	CG and non-CG	Promoter	Inhibition of transcription factor binding	Repression
	CG	Gene (less at 5' and 3' ends)	May reduce transcription elongation	Repression

Figure 6, modified after King (2015), shows the behavior of key components of DNA, histones, nucleosome and chromatin in the context of epigenetic marks and ionic environment of the plant nucleus. It indicates the importance of acetylation, a hall mark of gene activation, and shows the impact of histone acetyltransferases (HATs) and histone deacetylases (HDACs) on H3 and H4 acetylation.

Among other possible epigenetic changes upon UV-B exposure, histone modification plays an important role in UV-B mediated gene regulation. Histones are major protein components of chromatin, that package and order the genomic DNA into structural units

called nucleosomes. Histone octamers contain two copies of each histone protein: H2A, H2B, H3, and H4. They have an N-terminal tail which protrudes from the nucleosome, and is susceptible to specific post-translational modifications - "Histone tail modifications". In summary, they are the key control point of chromatin structure, hence the regulator of the interactions with proteins involved in transcription, DNA repair and replication (Chen et al.,2010; Jenkis,2009). When lysines at the N-terminal histone tails are acetylated, histone–DNA interactions are altered to make the DNA more accessible, leading to active transcription and gene activation. When lysines are deacetylated, DNA stays condensed and genes remain inactive (Kouzarides,2007). Thus, histone acetylation and deacetylation are essential for the regulation of plant gene expression (Loidl,2004). Histone H3 acetylation is of particular importance in gene activation. Furthermore, drought stress leads to an increase of H3K9ac at stress-responsive promoters (Kim et al.,2008b), suggesting that abiotic stress might generally facilitate histone acetylation.

1.5.2 Epigenetic modifications in MAMP triggered gene regulation

In *Arabidopsis*, pathogen attack up-regulates at least one histone deacetylase, suggesting an important role of histone acetylation/deacetylation in plant-pathogen interactions (De la Pena et al.,2012). For example Zhou et al. (2005) found that HISTONE DEACETYLASE 19 (HDA19) can be induced by the jasmonic acid (JA) and by 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC), leading to the up-regulation of chitinase and glucanase genes, and the increased resistance against *Alternaria brassicicola*. However, the effect of histone methylation on the pathogen defense related genes still remains unclear. Alvarez-Venegas et al. (2006) discovered that *Arabidopsis* trithorax-1 methyltransferase (ATX1) affects the expression of mildew-resistant factors, lectines, chaperones, heat shock proteins, and some WRKY TFs. WRKY70 was 7,2 fold down-regulated in the *atx1* mutant, showing the importance of ATX1 in WRKY70 gene activation, most likely by trimethylating the histone 3 lysine 4 (H3K4me3) of its nucleosomes. ChIP analysis showed that WRKY70 is the primary target of the ATX1 histone methylase activity, while SA and JA responsive genes - PR1 (PATHOGENESISRELATED GENE 1) and THI2.1 (THIONIN2.1), respectively, are its secondary targets. WRKY70 is involved in the cross-talk between SA and JA signaling pathways by up-regulating SA and down-regulating JA responsive genes. Interestingly in the *atx1* mutant, the expression of SA-responsive gene PR1 was significantly suppressed, and the expression of JA-responsive gene like THI2.1 was promoted, leading to a discovery of a novel regulatory mechanism mediated by ATX1 protein with a histone H3 lysine 4 methyltransferase activity (Alvarez-Venegas et al.,2007). Berr et al. (2010) discovered that the *Arabidopsis* ASH1 HOMOLOG 2 (ASHH2) protein has a vital role in plant defense against necrotrophic fungi by mediating the activation of JA/Ethylene signaling pathway genes via histone H3 lysine 36 trimethylation (H3K36me3). Furthermore, ASHH2 methyltransferase is necessary for maintaining the transcriptionally active state at LAZ5 (Palma et al.,2010) by modifying its chromatin at H3K36, and for basal and R-protein-mediated pathogen resistance in *Arabidopsis* (Palma et al.,2010). *Arabidopsis ash1* (absent, small or homeotic discs 1) - related mutants (ASHH2, ASHR1, ASHR3) were analyzed by De-La-Pena et al. (2012), to better understand the *Arabidopsis-Pseudomonas syringae* interaction on the epigenetic level. They found a higher resistance level in the *ashr3* mutant two days after the bacterial infection. Upon the infection they also found elevated expression level of the PR1 gene in the *ashr3* background, which was correlating to the previously noted increased resistance. Upon the infection, level of histone H3 lysine 4 dimethylation (H3K4me2) decreased at the promoter region of PR1 in

the *ashr1* and *ashh2* backgrounds, suggesting an involvement of epigenetically regulated PR1 gene in the plant defense. Luna et al. (2012) found that progeny from *Arabidopsis* inoculated with *Pseudomonas syringae pv tomato (Pst)* inherited the SAR from its parent, and was already primed to activate SA- inducible defense genes against *Pst* and *Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis*, and to reduce its responsiveness of JA- inducible genes. This shift in SA- and JA- dependent gene responsiveness was associated with H3K9ac enrichment at SA-inducible promoters of PATHOGENESIS-RELATED GENE1, WRKY6, and WRKY53 loci, and H3 triple methylation at lysine 27 at JA- inducible promoter of PLANT DEFENSIN 1.2 locus.

1.5.3 Chromatin modifications in UV-B mediated gene regulation

The ability to modify chromatin organization appears to also be important both in UV-B-induced gene expression responses and in evolutionary adaptation to elevated UV-B (Jenkins,2009). For example, UV-B-stimulated transcription of some *Arabidopsis* genes correlates with enrichment of diacetyl histone H3 (K9/K14), indicating that histone acetylation plays a role in UV-B-induced gene activation (Cloix and Jenkins,2008).

Some key components of the UV-signaling pathway DET1, and COP1 (essential component of UVR8 signaling) are involved in H3K9ac. Furthermore, histone modification enzymes acetyltransferases (HATs) and histone de-acetylases (HDACs) are involved in light-mediated gene transcription by integrating light signals to histone acetylation, suggesting a broad impact of histone modifications on light induced response in plants (Ralf Müller-Xing,2014). For example, Fina et al. (2015) showed that the histone acetyltransferase HAG3 affects the UV-B responses in *Arabidopsis* by down-regulating the expression of genes encoding for DNA repair enzymes and sunscreen content. The effect of histone acetylation on DNA repair enzymes was also documented by Campi et al. (2012), by pre-treating plants with curcumin - a HAT inhibitor, and observing deficiencies in DNA repair. They demonstrated as well, that *Arabidopsis* acetyltransferases HAM1 and HAM2 mutants showed increased DNA damage after a 4h UV-B treatment, suggesting that the role of these proteins in DNA damage repair has been conserved through evolution, as in humans. It has also been shown in maize, that histone acetylation and chromatin remodeling are required for UV-B-dependent transcriptional gene activation (Casati et al.,2008).

When exposed to UV-C and gamma irradiations, maize seedlings showed changes in satellite DNAm and chromatin structure. Changes in DNA methylation lead to differences in DNA vulnerability and its availability to transcription and repair factors (Sokolova et al.,2014). DNA methylation was also involved in Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), after exposing its seedlings to UV-B light. Using a method with two restriction enzymes HpaII and MspI, a general picture of changes in DNA methylation and not a quantification of the methylation level was acquired. After a week under the UV-B light, the level of DNAm was decreased in needles, reflecting a methylation changes in CCGG sequence (Ralf Müller-Xing,2014).

The bZIP TF HY5 plays a role of a master regulator in the light-induced transcriptional up-regulation of G- and Z- box containing promoters, by directly targeting some FPGs, or indirectly by activating other TFs, including MYB12 (Lee et al.,2007; Stracke et al.,2010). An increase in H3K9ac at HY5 locus and its downstream targets is associated with plant

exposure to the light, as seen by Guo et al. (2008). Furthermore, in the Arabidopsis loss of function mutants of the RPD3-type histone deacetylase HDA1, levels of H3K9ac at the loci of light-regulated genes (including CHS) were found to be raised, indication that HDA1 could remove H3K9ac at those loci (Benhamed et al.,2006; Guo et al.,2008). Apart from HDA1, its most closely related histone deacetylase HDA6 was also found to participate in the chromatin organization (Tessadori et al.,2009). In Arabidopsis the effect of HDA1 and HDA6 might be additive, since they were reported to play partially redundant roles in mediating abiotic stress responses such as ABA- and salt stress-induced gene expression (Tanaka et al.,2008; Chen and Wu,2010). On the other hand, histone acetyltransferases HAT1 and HAF2 can regulate together H3K9, H3K27, and H3K12 acetylation, and have a pivotal role in light induced gene activation, while H3K12 depends merely on HAT1 (Benhamed et al.,2006; Earley et al.,2007). However in the *hat1* or *haf2* mutant, CHS expression level and histone acetylation pattern of its promoter remained unaffected, only to be slightly reduced in *hat1 haf2* double mutant, which could mean that more genes with functional redundancy are involved in CHS activation (Benhamed et al.,2006). Since HY5 can up regulate CHS by directly binding to its promoter, or via MYB12 activation (Lee et al.,2007; Stracke et al.,2010), but also as Servet et al. (2010) proposes by possibly recruiting HAT1 to acetylate the histones on the core promoter regions of light-responsive genes, the role of histone acetylation in the regulation of FPGs seems to be crucial.

1.6 Aim of this work and working hypothesis

1.6.1 Establishing a working system to investigate the crosstalk between UV-B and MAMP (flg22) triggered immunity in plants (Arabidopsis, maize)

Since more than 20 years, knowledge regarding this crosstalk comes from experiments involving treatments of protoplast or cell cultures with pathogen derived crude elicitors (Dangl et al.,1987; Lozoya et al.,1991; Logemann and Hahlbrock 2002; Gläßgen et al.,1998). Furthermore, the reduction in flavonol and anthocyanin biosynthesis has been detected in onion and sorghum after inoculation with *Botrytis allii* and *Cochliobolus heterostrophus*, respectively (Lo and Nicholson,1998; McLusky et al.,1999), indicating that this might be a common mechanism used by plants. Since Schenke et al. (2011) observed a functional crosstalk in Arabidopsis Col-0 cell culture treated with UV-B light and concomitantly with flg22, it should be also possible to establish the same working system in *Arabidopsis thaliana* plants. Moreover, a maize homolog of Arabidopsis flg22 receptor FLS2 has already been identified *in silico* (Supplementary Figure S3), thus it is reasonable to believe that transferring the system to maize plants will work as well.

1.6.2 Dissection of the crosstalk

MYB12 and MYB4 are conversely regulated by both UV-B and flg22 stress. MYB12 is up-regulated by UV-B and then down-regulated by the concomitant treatment with flg22. MYB4 is activated by UV-B light (in a feedback inhibitory manner via MYB12), and also by flg22 MAMP. However, MYB4 is activated much earlier in response to flg22 than to UV-B light. This might mean that during the PTI, MYB4 takes up a role to quickly down-regulate MYB12, and by that shut down the flavonol production (Schenke et al.,2011). Treating *myb4* and *myb12* mutant Arabidopsis plants with UV-B and concomitantly with flg22 should shed light on how the flavonoid pathway is shut down.

Figure 7, from Schenke and Cai (2014). Working model showing the interaction of transcription factors in the regulation of the flavonol pathway genes. The UV-B up-regulated FPG expression might be suppressed by flg22 signaling through WRKY TFs which down-regulate the positive regulator MYB12 and/or activate the negative regulator MYB4. Down the road, MYBs could recruit HATs or HDACs and shut down the flavonol production either by preventing H3K9 acetylation (MYB12 suppression) or enforcing H3K9 deacetylation (MYB4 activation) at the FPG loci.

2) Materials and methods

2.1 Plant material

Experiments were carried out with *Arabidopsis thaliana* Col-0 ecotype, three mutant lines (details in the Table 2 below), and the susceptible maize variety "Lorado".

Table 2: Overview of Arabidopsis lines used in the experiment

Genotype	Gene function, comment
Col-0	wild type, control
<i>fls2</i>	flg22 receptor, positive control
<i>myb4</i>	transcription factor, negative regulator, involved in UV-B response
<i>myb12</i>	transcription factor, positive regulator, involved in UV-B induced flavonoid biosynthesis

2.2 Growth conditions

Arabidopsis seeds were planted in Jiffy-7 Peat Pellets (Jiffy Products International AS, Norway). Seeds were kept at 4°C for 48h before being transferred to the growth chamber, in order to go through the vernalization process and emerge simultaneously. After two weeks spent in the growth chamber at 20°C under short-day conditions (8h light), young seedlings were singled out (again in Jiffys).

Plants used for genotyping were analyzed as described below. Positive plants were grown together with wild type and positive control for propagation.

For seed production, in the fourth/fifth week, when the rosette growth was completed, and the first flower buds were visible in the rosette, the plants were transferred to the greenhouse for growing under long-day conditions. After bolting, during the fifth/sixth week, when more than 50% of the flowers were opened, seed collecting bags were wrapped around the inflorescence. During the seventh week, siliques were ripened in the bags, seed pods became brown and shattered later on. Seeds were collected and replanted for the treatments. The same growth procedure was repeated. For the treatment experiment, plants were grown nine per pot. Maize seeds were planted two per pot (also in Jiffys). Plants were not genotyped, but used in the treatment experiment only.

2.3 Genotyping

2.3.1 DNA isolation

Couple of small leaves were cut from the plants (Col-0 WT, *myb4*, and *myb12*) and placed into the 1.5 ml tube. Tubes were frozen in liquid nitrogen, and afterwards the tissue inside was grinded to fine powder using the Micro Pestle. To each tube, 400 μ l of extraction buffer was added and well mixed with the powder. Centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 5 minutes followed, and around 300 μ l of supernatant was transferred to a clean tube. Same amount (300 μ l) of 2-propanol was added, tubes were well vortexed, and again centrifuged at 14000 rpm for 5 minutes. Supernatant was carefully discarded, and the pellet was rinsed with 700 μ l of 70% ethanol for 10 minutes. Afterwards tubes were drained, and the pellet was allowed to dry out for 30 minutes at 37°C. Later on, pellet was dissolved in 50 μ l of TE Buffer. DNA of the WT and mutant lines was used for genotyping. Details for the Extraction and TE buffer preparation can be found below:

Extraction buffer

200 mM Tris-Cl (pH 7.5)
250 mM NaCl
25 mM EDTA
0.5% SDS

TE buffer

10 mM Tris-Cl (pH 8.0)
1 mM EDTA

2.3.2 How to genotype

Verification that the mutant lines are indeed homozygous is a prerequisite for any further experiments. It can be done using the three primers LP, RP, and LBb1.3. For WT detection, LP-RP primer combination is used and band around 1000bps in size is visualized on the gel. For HM (Homozygous line) detection, RP-LB combination is used and band of 410 bps in size or bigger (depending on "N") is visible on the gel. These 410 bps represent the distance between the RP and the insertion site (300bps) plus 110 bps from LBb1.3 to the left border of the vector. "N" ranges from 0-300 bps. To detect HZ (Heterozygous) line, both LP-RP and LB-RP primer combinations are used. HZ line shows two bands on the gel (410+N bps band coming from the chromosome with an insertion, and 900 bps band coming from untouched chromosome) (<http://signal.salk.edu>).

1. Protocol for SALK T-DNA primer design

MaxN - Maximum difference of the actual insertion site and the sequence (300 bps)

pZone - Regions used to pick up primers (100 bps)

Ext5, Ext3 - Regions between the MaxN to pZone (not for picking primers)

LP, RP - Left, Right genomic primer

BP - T-DNA border primer

BPos - The distance from BP to the insertion site

Figure 8, from signal.salk.edu. T-DNA primer design.

In order to identify the primer position and the T-DNA insertion, in TAIR's sequence viewer (nucleotide view), T-DNA/Tn insertion was chosen to be a highlighted object within a *myb12* (AT2G47460) and *myb4* (AT4G38620) genes.

Figure 9, from www.arabidopsis.org. MYB12 (AT2G47460) sequence with the indicated SALK_046675.29.75.X T-DNA insert location (T-DNA annotation appears below the sequence) and the forward and reverse primer of the insert (highlighted in blue and described in detail below).

Figure 10, from www.arabidopsis.org. MYB4 (AT4G38620.1) sequence with the indicated Enhancer Trap ET3967.DS3.12.06.99.B.477 insert location (Enhancer Trap annotation appears below the sequence) and its forward and reverse primer. (highlighted in blue and described in detail below)

Primer details:

MYB12 (N665933), SALK_046675C
 myb12 SALK LP CACGAGGTTCTCTTATTCCCC
 myb12 RTE rev TACAATCCAAACATCCCATGG
 Product size 1130 bp
 Insert size 552-852 bp

MYB4 (N26404), ET3967 enhancer trap (ET) transposable Ds element in LER
 myb4 ET3967 forward CTTATTGCCGGGAGATTACC
 MYB4 rte reverse TCCATTGCTCATGTCACTCC
 Product size 507 bp
 Insert size 514 bp

2.3.3 Touch-Down PCR

Isolated DNA was used for Touchdown PCR (Figure 11) to amplify MYB4 and MYB12 genes in Col-0 WT (control), check if they are present in mutant lines and amplify T-DNA insertions in *myb4* and *myb12* mutant lines. Touchdown PCR was used in order to increase the specificity and unwanted unspecific binding of the primers. Annealing temperature during the first cycles of touchdown PCR is higher than the optimal for primer annealing. However, in these conditions only the highly specific primers can bind to the template (sequence of interest). These fragments will be promoted and further amplified during the subsequent cycles (when the temperature gradually decreases). Like that, sequence of interest will out compete the non-specific ones (Korbie and Mattic,2008).

Figure 11, showing the Touch-Down PCR program used to amplify MYB12 and MYB4

2.4 Treatment with elevated UV-B light and flg22/water

As discussed before, nine Arabidopsis plants per pot were singled out and grown in Jiffys for treatment experiment. Treatment was done when the plants were three/four weeks of age. Maize plants were used four/five days after the seed emergence. In order to get clear measurable statistical data, plants were collected and put into darkness two days before the treatment. In those conditions, level of CHS went down, so the induction during the concomitant exposure to UV-B can be clearly registered. Flg22 solution was also prepared beforehand. For one treatment around 50 mg of synthesized peptides (powder) were measured, and dissolved in 20 ml of water to reach the flg22 concentration of 1000 μM . Plants on the tray were separated in two groups. Organization on the tray can be seen in the Figure 12 (B, C) below. First group on the left side was sprayed with 20 ml of water. Second group on the right was sprayed with 20 ml of flg22. Afterwards, the incubation period of 2h in the darkness at room temperature followed. Then, the plants were positioned on the tray and covered with the glass plate. Around 1cm of space was left between the glass plate and the tray for the better air circulation. Tray was transferred into UV-box equipped with two broadband UV-B lamps with an emission spectrum from 290 to 315 nm (TL 20W/12 RS, Philips, Eindhoven, Netherlands) and two lamps (PLSL 18W/21, PROTEC.class, Eschborn, Germany) for white light supply, where it stayed for 6 hours. Harvesting the plant material was done immediately after.

Figure 12, showing elements of the Treatment experiment. A) Nine Arabidopsis plants per pot, ready for the treatment. B) Distribution of Arabidopsis and maize plants on the tray - left side was treated with H₂O, right side with flg22. C) Glass plate on top of the tray to minimize the UV-B direct damage to plant tissue; plants ready for the UV box. D) UV box

2.5 Harvest and Storage of plant material

Nine whole Arabidopsis seedlings from each pot were pooled in the 1.5 ml tubes. Tubes were immediately frozen in the liquid nitrogen and afterwards stored at -80°C . Plants were harvested using the clean forceps and the soil particles were removed from the roots by dragging the plants through the petri dish filled with water. Maize leaves, along with the stems were cut using scissors and put into 50 ml tubes, which were also immediately frozen.

2.6 RNA isolation

Total RNA was isolated using the innuPREP PLANT RNA Kit. Samples were taken out from the freezer, and in the constant presence of liquid nitrogen, grinded to fine powder using the mortar and pestle. Without allowing the sample to thaw, powder was transferred to 1,5 ml reaction tubes, which were right away frozen in the liquid nitrogen and afterwards stored in the freezer at -80°C . On the day of RNA isolation samples were taken out, and 450 μl of Lysis Solution PL was immediately added into the tubes. Samples were incubated for further lysis under constant shaking for 5 minutes. Unlysed material was spinned down by centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 1 minute. Blue Spin Filter D was placed into 2.0 ml Receiver Tube and supernatant of the lysed sample was transferred onto it. Centrifugation at 12000 rpm for 2 minutes followed, and the Spin Filter D was discarded. Filtrate was preserved because it contains RNA. Violet Spin Filter R was placed into a new 2.0 ml Receiver Tube. An approximately equal amount of 400 μl of 70% DEPC treated ethanol was added to the filtrate from the previous step. Sample was mixed by pipetting up and down, and then transferred onto already prepared Spin Filter R. Tubes were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 2 minutes. The 2 ml Receiver Tube with filtrate was discarded and the Spin Filter R was placed into a new 2.0 ml Receiver Tube. Now 500 μl of Washing Solution HS was added onto the Spin Filter R, and the tubes were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 1 minute. The Receiver Tube with filtrate was discarded and the Spin Filter R was placed into a new 2.0 ml Receiver Tube. Then 650 μl of Washing Solution LS was added and tubes were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 1 minute. Receiver Tube with filtrate was discarded and the Spin Filter R was placed into a new 2.0 ml Receiver Tube. Again 650 μl of Washing Solution LS was added onto Spin Filter R, and tubes were centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 1 minute. Receiver Tube with filtrate was discarded and the Spin Filter R was placed into a new 2.0 ml Receiver Tube. Centrifugation at 12000 rpm for 2 minutes followed to remove all traces of ethanol, after which the 2.0 Receiver Tube was discarded. The Spin Filter R was placed into a 1.5 ml Elution Tube and 40 μl of RNase-free water was added onto it. Sample was incubated for 1 minute and then centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 1 minute. Around 40 μl of transparent liquid containing RNA was collected in 1.5 ml Elution Tubes. The concentration and quality of RNA were checked using NanoDrop and gel electrophoresis, respectively.

2.6.1 RNA quality and concentration check

MOPS buffer was used to prepare 1.3% agarose gel. For the 100 ml of gel, 2 μl of ethidiumbromide were added. Mixture of 2 μl of RNA, 16 μl of DEPC-water and 2 μl of 10X loading buffer was pipetted into the wells of agarose gel, parameters were set to 110V for 30min, and the electrophoresis started. RNA concentration was checked using NanoVue

Plus spectrophotometer. Around 1000ng/ μ l of RNA concentration was required. Isolated RNA was diluted to the factor of 10 for concentration check. Device was first tared using HPLC water. Concentration of RNA was measured 2-3 times using 2.5ul of the sample.

2.7 cDNA synthesis

cDNA was synthesized using Thermo Scientific RevertAid cDNA Synthesis Kit. The procedure consists of two separate steps: Removal of genomic DNA from RNA preparations and First Strand cDNA synthesis.

For RT-PCR application template RNA was purified from the DNA contamination. Prior to cDNA synthesis, 1 μ g of RNA, 1 μ l of 10X reaction Buffer with $MgCl_2$, 1 μ l of RNase-free DNase I and enough of nuclease-free water to reach the total volume of 10 μ l, were added to RNase-free tube. Samples were incubated at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 minutes. Afterwards, 1 μ l of 50 mM EDTA was added and incubation was continued at 65 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 minutes. Prepared RNA in tubes was put on ice and further used for reverse transcription.

1 μ l of Oligo (dt)₁₈ primer was added and samples were incubated at 65 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes, and then put back on ice. Following reagents were added in a following order: 4 μ l of 5x Reaction Buffer, 1 μ l of RiboLock RNase Inhibitor (20 U/ μ l) and 2 μ l of 10 mM dNTP Mix. Samples were mixed gently and finally 1 μ l RevertAid M-MuLV RT (200 U/ μ l) was added. Total volume in tubes of 20 μ l was incubated firstly at 42 $^{\circ}$ C for 60 minutes, and then right after at 70 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes. The reverse transcription products were checked by PCR amplification of the house-keeping gene *AtACTIN2* (*AtACT2*), and afterwards stored at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.

2.7.1 Amplification of the house-keeping gene *AtACT2* to check cDNA quality

cDNA quality was checked by amplifying Actin2 housekeeping gene, with following primers

Forward: ACCTTGCTGGACGTGACCTTACTGAT

Reverse: GTTGTCTCGTGGATTCCAGCAGCTT

Master mix was prepared as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: PCR Master mix preparation

Reagent	Amount for one reaction (μ l)
cDNA template (1:10 diluted)	2.0
dNTPs 100 mM (1:10)	2.0
primer mix (forward and reverse)	2.0
HPLC water	11.5
DreamTaq Buffer 10x	2.0
DreamTaq DNA Polymerase 5 U/ μ l	0.5

Reaction mix was transferred into each reaction tube (20 µl/tube) and PCR reaction was started. Program used for amplification of *AtACT 2* is showed in the Table 4.

Table 4: Touch-down PCR program used to amplify *AtACT2*

Step	Temperature (°C)	Time	Number of cycles
Initial Denaturation	95	20s	1
Denaturation	95	20s	25
Annealing	55	20s	
storage	4	forever	

After the amplification, 4 µl of 6x Thermo Scientific Loading Dye were added to PCR reaction tubes. Half of the total volume (12 µl) was pipetted into agarose gel wells for gel electrophoresis. Alongside with PCR products, 10 µl of 100bp Thermo Scientific GeneRuler DNA Ladder was run.

2.8 Expression analysis using the Real Time-qPCR

Real Time PCR was performed using the Maxima SYBR Green/ROX qPCR Master Mix from Thermo Scientific. Details of the master mix are shown below:

10 µl -> SYBR Green

4 µl -> Primer mix

4 µl -> nuclease-free water-use

Two technical repeats were conducted for each sample. Negative controls and melt curve analysis were also performed to ensure the target specific amplification. In the wells of the reaction plate 18 µl of the Master Mix with 2 µl of template were pipetted. Expression profile of CHS, PP2A (house-keeping gene) and FRK1 (flg22-induced receptor-like kinase) in Col-0 WT and mutant lines (*fls2*, *myb4*, and *myb12*) was analyzed. Primer information is indicated in Table 5 and Supplement figure S1 (A-C). In maize (Lorado), transcriptional profiling of housekeeping gene Protein Phosphatase 2 (PP2A) and chalcone synthase genes WHP1 and C2 was performed. Primer information is indicated in Table 6 and Supplement figure S2 (A-C). Analysis was done on C1000 Touch Thermal Cycler - CFX96 Real-Time System from BIO RAD, using the Touch-Down PCR program as depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13 showing the Real Time-qPCR program used to amplify PP2A, CHS, and FRK1 in Arabidopsis ecotype and mutants; and PP2A, WHP1, and C2 in maize

Table 5: Primers used in the expression analysis of CHS, FRK1 and PP2A in Arabidopsis ecotype and mutant lines

PP2A	Fw:CAATGACGATGACGATGAGGTG	Rv:ATGCTCAACCAAGTCACTCTC	208bp
CHS	Fw: GTTCAAGCGCATGTGCGACAAG	Rv: GCCGCTTCTTTGCCTAGCTTA	165bp
FRK1	Fw:GGTTGTAAGCCTCCTATAGTTCAC	Rv:TGAAATCTGACCGCTTCCTTCAC	132bp

Table 6: Primers used in the expression analysis of PP2A, WHP1, and C2 in maize

PP2A	Fw: GAAGCGCCTGGAGGAAATGG	Rv: CGTGACTGGGTTTGCCATTG	80bp
WHP1	Fw: TGTTCCAGCTCGTGTGGCG	Rv:CCTTGAGCAGGTGGAACGTC	102bp
C2	Fw: TCTTCCAGCTCGTCTCCGCC	Rv:CCTTGAGCAGGTGGAAGGG	102bp

3) Results

3.1 Genotyping of mutants

Products of the Touch-Down PCR were separated at 75V on the 1,3% agarose gel (Figure 13)

Figure 14, Genotyping experiment showing that *myb12* and *myb4* are homozygous mutant lines. Primers for the MYB4 and MYB4 ET transposable element amplification were used on the left side of Figure (left from the ladder); MYB12 and MYB12 T-DNA primers were used on the right side (right from the ladder). Wild Type (WT) (507 bp) signal in the first lane (from the left) shows the amplified MYB4 gene in the Arabidopsis Col-0 ecotype (LP+RP primer combination). No signal in the second lane was expected, for there should be no T-DNA insertion (amplified with LBb 1.3 + RP primer combination) in the Col-0. In the third lane, MYB4 was amplified in the *myb4* mutant line, hence no signal was obtained. Fourth lane shows the presence of the T-DNA insertion (LBb 1.3 + RP) in the *myb4* line. MYB12 signal (around 1130 bp) was obtained in the Col-0 WT (fifth lane). No T-DNA insert signal was found in Col-0 (sixth lane). No signal of MYB12 gene in the *myb12* line (seventh lane). There is a T-DNA insertion in the *myb12* line (eighth lane).

3.2 Gene expression analysis

3.2.1 RNA isolation and cDNA synthesis

Total RNA was successfully isolated from the plants treated with UV-B light and the

combination of UV-B and flg22 (F/U). Two prominent 28s and 18s bands were visualized on the 1,3% agarose gel at 70V (Figure 14a showing one plant batch out of three). The Figure 14b shows amplified house-keeping *AtACT2* gene (298 bp) in the synthesized cDNA (corresponding lanes between RNA and cDNA).

Figure 15, showing the isolated RNA (a) from the plant material, used later for the cDNA synthesis (b).

3.2.2 RT-qPCR assays

Figure 16, showing the expression profile of WHP1 and C2. The level of both maize chalcone synthase gene copies did not drop down after concomitant treatment with flg22, and the functional cross-talk was not observed, most likely due to the inability of maize plants to perceive flg22 elicitor.

Figure 17, Expression profile of CHS and FRK1 (control) in Col-0 ecotype. Level of CHS dropped down after concomitant elicitation with flg22. This data already shows functional cross-talk in Arabidopsis. As expected, no up-regulation of FRK1 (flg22-induced receptor like kinase) was observed after treatment with UV-B light since it is not a light-responsive gene. Expression of FRK1 went up after co-treatment with flg22, indicating that flg22 elicitor used was indeed recognized by the plant.

Figure 18, Expression profile of CHS and FRK1 in Arabidopsis *fls2* mutant lines. Level of CHS did not significantly drop down after co-treatment with flg22, because the main Arabidopsis flg22 receptor FLS2 is knocked-out in the mutant line. As expected, FRK1 was not induced by UV-B light, nor by the flg22 co-treatment (induction of FRK1 in the F/U treatment was not statistically significant, supporting the fact that flg22 cannot be perceived without FLS2 receptor).

Figure 19, Expression profile of CHS and FRK1 in Arabidopsis *myb12* mutant lines. Level of CHS dropped down after concomitant flg22 treatment. Unexpectedly, cross-talk wasn't impaired, and works like in wild type, implying that MYB12 in spite of predictions, doesn't play a key role in UV-B-flg22 signal cross-talk. FRK1 wasn't induced by the UV-B, and was up-regulated by F/U, as expected.

Figure 20, Expression profile of CHS and FRK1 in Arabidopsis *myb4* mutant lines. Like in *myb12*, no cross-talk impairment was detected, suggesting that MYB4 doesn't play a key role in UV-B-flg22 signal cross-talk as well.

Error bars represent the standard deviation of duplicate experiments, and statistical significance (* $p \leq 0.05$ / ** $p \leq 0.01$) was checked by t-test ($n=3$).

4) Results discussion

4.1 *Arabidopsis thaliana* as a model system for studying the UVB-flg22 signal cross talk

The UV-B induced production of flavonols was suppressed by the co-treatment with flg22 in *Arabidopsis thaliana* Col-0 wild type, meaning that *Arabidopsis* can be used as a suitable model plant in the research. The *fls2* mutant line can be used as the control for the future, since flg22 couldn't be perceived in the absence of the main receptor FLS2, resulting in impairment of the cross-talk (Figure 18). Maize plants (Lorado) were also treated with UV-B alone and in combination with flg22, and the expression level of two duplicated *Zea mays* chalcone synthase genes C2 and WHP1 was measured (Figure 16). However, no functional cross talk was noted in any of the copies although the maize homolog of *Arabidopsis* flg22 receptor FLS2 was identified *in silico* (shown in Supplement figure S3). Since the same elicitor (coming from the same source) was able to trigger the suppression of flavonol production in *Arabidopsis*, we are led to believe that flg22 hasn't been/can't be recognized by the maize plants. On the other hand the combination of elevated UV-B light and flg22 stresses in the duration of 6h was found to be sufficient for *Arabidopsis* to suppress the expression of Chalcone synthase (CHS). This key enzyme of the flavonoid biosynthesis pathway and FLG22-induced receptor-like kinase 1 (FRK1) were found to be good marker genes to investigate the cross-talk and the successful flg22 treatment as shown in Figure 17.

4.2 The key role TFs MYB12 and MYB4 in the UVB-flg22 signal cross-talk

Unexpectedly, after analyzing the expression of CHS and FRK1 in *myb12* and *myb4* mutants, impaired cross-talk was not detected, implying that these two TFs may not be as important as speculated. However, in the *myb12* background, functional cross-talk was maybe observed because of the functional redundancy of positive MYB regulators (MYB11, MYB111, and MYB12) which act in an additive manner due to their differential spatial activity. It could be speculated that MYB11 and MYB111 are taking up the role of flavonol pathway regulation in the absence of MYB12. Stracke et al. (2007) found that MYB12 is located mainly in *Arabidopsis* roots, and MYB111 and MYB11 in the cotyledons and seedling nodal areas, respectively. This differential spatial activity of MYBs might also be the reason for the obtained data in *myb12* background, although the whole seedlings were sampled for the RNA extraction. Myb4 was speculated to play a role in shutting the flavonol pathway down by recruiting HDACs to remove H3K9ac from flavonol loci, and by suppressing HAT recruiting TFs like MYB12. Both scenarios contribute to the deacetylated H3K9 state, however, since no impairing effect on the cross-talk was observed in *myb4* mutant background it can be maybe speculated that prevention of histone acetylation via *myb12/11/111* has a more important role.

4.3 Future perspectives

Since a functional system in Arabidopsis has now been established, a complete picture regarding signaling in this cross-talk can be created by involving some other mutants like *hy5*, *hyh*, and WRKYs because of the putative roles which they play in this cross-talk. Furthermore, some chromatin mutants, such as histone acetylases and deacetylases could be tested as well. In order to be sure about the effect of MYB positive regulators on the cross-talk, further analysis in *myb11/12/111* triple mutant plants are suggested. This will exclude the possibility that these three MYB TFs have worked together to positively affect the transcription of FPGs. When UV-B and bacterial pathogen stress (mimicked by *flg22*) come at the same time, cross-talk in plants functions in a way that it stops the flavonol "sunscreen" production and focuses on the defense against bacteria. It seems that plants recognize pathogens as a more urgent treat that needs to be dealt with. Once the plant has started preparing its defense, it is already harder for the bacteria to successfully invade and colonize the plant tissue. Hence, it can be concluded that pathogens will benefit if the cross-talk is impaired. Moreover, we hypothesize that bacteria can use effector proteins to interfere with one or more components of PTI and suppress the cross-talk. In order to investigate this hypothesis, instead of elicitation with *flg22*, a pathosystem between Arabidopsis and bacteria could be established in the future. Pathosystem between Arabidopsis and *Pseudomonas syringae* has been developed for more than two decades (Dong et al.,1991) and has been successfully used until today to study Arabidopsis-bacteria interactions. The two virulent strains most widely used today, *P. syringae* pv. *tomato* DC3000 and *P. syringae* pv. *maculicola* ES4326, originated from these early studies and could be also good candidates for the cross-talk research.

5) Summary

Abiotic stress coming from elevated UV-B light induces the production of flavonols in *Arabidopsis*. Their accumulation is suppressed by the concomitant pathogen attack simulated by bacteria derived elicitor flg22. The amount of accumulated flavonol metabolites is in correlation with the level of CHS protein, transcript level of all co-regulated phenylpropanoid genes involved in flavonol synthesis, and the increase in histone H3 lysine 9 acetylation (H3K9ac) at the promoter and open reading frame of phenylpropanoid genes like CHS, CFI (chalcone flavone isomerase family protein), F3H (flavanone 3- hydroxylase) and the positive regulator MYB12 in *Arabidopsis thaliana* Col-0 cell culture (Schenke et al.,2011). Furthermore, it was found that flg22 elicitation mediates the suppression of all flavonol pathway genes, indicating the presence of a common mechanism which operates the co-regulation in response to UV-B and concomitant flg22 stress (Schenke et al.,2011). The first goal of thesis was to establish a working system in plants like *Arabidopsis* and maize, in order to investigate this phenomenon more in detail. Apart from transcriptional reprogramming, the ability to modify chromatin organization seems to be of evolutionary importance in plant adaptation to elevated UV-B light. It was also found to play a pivotal role in UV-B induced gene expression responses. For example, the importance of histone acetylation in UV-B induced gene activation was noted by Cloix and Jenkis (2008), whereby UV-B mediated up-regulation of some *Arabidopsis* genes was found to be in a correlation with the enrichment of diacetyl histone H3 (K9/K14) at the respected loci. Furthermore, it is known that some TFs can interact with HATs (Servet et al.,2008), therefore it is reasonable to believe that they could recruit HAT activity to their targets and facilitate gene activation in that way. Reports from Mao et al. (2006) and Gao et al. (2007), which show that various TFs can recruit and lead HAT1 to specific gene promoters are supporting this hypothesis. On the other hand, some TFs such as WRKYs can interact with HDACs (HDA1), and take up a role of transcriptional repressors (Gonzalez et al.,2007; Kim et al.,2008). Similarly, report from Bowen et al. (2010) shows that some proteins which contain MYB domain are interacting with SNL1 proteins in yeast-three-hybrid system to recruit HDAC activity. This leads us to believe that apart from HATs, HDACs could be recruited as well, and brought to genes containing the respective cis-elements in their promoters in order to affect their activation negatively by preventing histone acetylation. Second goal: since it was assumed that TFs MYB12 and MYB4 can recruit positively and negatively regulating chromatin remodeling factors to flavonol pathway gene loci, the analysis of *Arabidopsis myb12* and *myb4* mutant plants should enable a clear dissection of this cross-talk and help in predicting the reaction of plants to the changing environmental conditions. Maize and *Arabidopsis* (Col-0 WT, and genotyped homozygous *myb12*, *myb4*, and *fls2* mutant lines) seedlings were treated with UV-B alone and in combination with flg22. In the results, functional cross-talk wasn't observed in maize, most likely due to the inability of *Zea mays* to perceive flg22, but *Arabidopsis* was found to be a suitable plant for system establishment and cross-talk investigation. Using *myb12* and *myb4* mutants in the experiment, the light was shed on how the flavonol pathway is being shut down. Unexpectedly, impaired cross-talk was not detected in *myb12* and *myb4* background, implying that these two TFs may not be as important as speculated. However, more future research needs to be done in the future in order to have a clearer picture of how this cross-talk is being regulated.

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7) Supplement Figures

Arabidopsis thaliana nucleotide sequence of CHS (AT5G13930)

ATGGTGATGGCTGGTGCTTCTTCTTTGGATGAGATCAGACAGGCTCAGAGAGCTGATGGACCTGCAGG
 CATCTTGGCTATTGGCACTGCTAACCCTGAGAACCATGTGCTTCAGGCGGAGTATCCTGACTACTACTT
 CCGCATCACCAACAGTGAACACATGACCGACCTCAAGGAGAA **GTTCAAGCGCATGTGCGACAAG**TCGA
 CAATTCGAAACGTACATGCATCTGACGGAGGAATTCCTCAAGGAAAACCCACACATGTGTGCTTACA
 TGGCTCCTTCTCTGGACACCAGACAGGACATCGTGGTGGTCAAGTCCC **TAAGCTAGGCAAAGAAGCG**
GCAGTGAAGGCCATCAAGGAGTGGGGCCAGCCCAAGTCAAAGATCACTCATGTCGTCTTCTGCACTAC
 CTCCGGCGTCGACATGCCTGGTGTGCTGACTACCAGCTCACCAAGCTTCTTGGTCTCCGTCCTTCCGTCAA
 GCGTCTCATGATGTACCAGCAAGGTTGCTTCGCCGGCGGTAAGTGTCTCCGTATCGCTAAGGATCTCG
 CCGAGAACAATCGTGGAGCACGTGTCTCGTTGTCTGCTCTGAGATCACAGCCGTTACCTTCCGTGGTC
 CCTCTGACACCCACCTTGACTCCCTCGTCGGTCAGGCTCTTTTCAGTGATGGCGCCGCCGCACTCATTG
 TGGGGTCCGACCCCTGACACATCTGTCCGAGAGAAACCCATCTTTGAGATGGTGTCTGCCGCTCAGACC
 ATCCTTCCAGACTCTGATGGTGCCATAGACGGACATTTGAGGGAAAGTTGGTCTCACCTTCCATCTCCTC
 AAGGATGTTCCCGGCCCTCATCTCCAAGAACATTGTGAAGAGTCTAGACGAAGCGTTTAAACCTTTGGGG
 ATAAGTGAAGTGAAGTCCCTCTTCTGGATAGCCACCCTGGAGGTCCAGCGATCCTAGACCAGGTGGA
 GATAAAGCTAGGACTAAAGGAAGAGAAGATGAGGGCGACACGTCACGTGTTGAGCGAGTATGGAACA
 TGTCGAGCGCGTGCCTTCTTTCATACTAGACGAGATGAGGAGGAAGTCAGCTAAGGATGGTGTGGCC
 ACGACAGGAGAAGGGTTGGAGTGGGGTGTCTTGTGTTTCGGACCAGGTCTCACTGTTGAGACAGT
 CGTCTTGCACAGCGTTCCTCTCTAA

Supplement figure S1A: indicating the position of *At*CHS forward and reverse primer in the CHS nucleotide sequence

Arabidopsis thaliana nucleotide sequence of FRK1 (AT2G19190)

ATGGCGATGTTAAAATCTCTTTCATCGATTTTATTCACAAGCTTTGCTCTTCTGTTCTTTCTTGTTCATGCT
 CAAGATCAATCTGGTTTCATAAGTATAGATTGCGGGATACCGGATGATTCTAGCTACAACGATGAGACTA
 CAGGTATAAAGTATGTTTCGGATTTCGGCGTTTGTGATTGAGGAACAACAAGAGAATTGCAGCTCAGTT
 TCAATCAAGTGGTTTTGATAGACACTTGTGAACGTGAGAAGTTTCCCTCAAAGCAAGAGAAGCTGTTAC
 GATGTTCCGACGCCGAGAGGCAAAGGTTTTAAGTATCTAATCAGAAGTCTGTTTCATGTACGGGAAGTAT
 GATGATCTTGGAAAGTACCCGAGTTCGATCTCTATCTAGGAGTAAACTTTTGGGACTCTGTTAAACTCG
 ACGATGCAACAACATACTCAACAAGAGATAATCACCATTCCACTTTTAGACAATGTTCAAGTGTGTGTT
 GTTGATAAGAACGCAGGAAGTCCATTTTTGTCTGTCTTGGAGATACGGCTCTTGTGAACTACTTATG
 AGACTCCTTACGATGCACTTACCCTCCTTCGGAGATTAGATTACAGCAAAACGGGAAAACCTTCCATCGA
 GGTACAAAGATGACATATATGACCGTATATGGACACCGCGTATAGTGAGTTCAGAATACAAGATATTA
 TACATCTCTCACTGTGATCAATTTCTTAACAATGGCTACCAACCGGCTTCTACTGTGATGAGCACTGCA
 GAAACAGCGCGAAACGAGAGCCTCTACCTAACGCTTAGTTTCAGACCGCCCGACCCTAACGCAAAGTTT
 TATGTATACATGCACTTTGCTGAAATTGAAGTACTGAAAAGCAACCAGACGAGAGAATTCAGCATCTGGC
 TAAATGAGGATGTAATCTCTCCTTCGTTTAAAGTTCGGTACTTGTACTTACCGACACATTGCTTCCACCGGAT
 ATTAACGCCCTTGGAGTCTATCAAGTCAATGAGTTCCTTCAGATCCCAACTCATCCACAGGATGTTGATG
 CCATGAGGAAGATTAAAGCCACGTATAGAGTGAAGAAGAAGTGGCAAGGAGATCCTTTGTTCCCGTAG
 ATTATTCTTGGGAAGGATTGACTGTATCCAAAGTGATAACACTACTAATCCTAGAGTCGTTTCACTAAAT
 ATATCTTTTAGTGAATTAAGAGGCCAGATAGATCCAGCCTTCTCCAACCTTACATCTATAAGAAAATTAGA
 TTTATCCGGTAATACTTTAACAGGAGAAATACCTGCTTTCCTCGCTAACTTACCAACTTGACCGAATTA
 ACGTTGAAGGAAACAAGTTAACGGGCATAGTTCCACAAGATTGCATGAAAGATCAAAGAATGGATCTC
 TTTCTTAAAGATTTGGTAGAAATCCGGACCTTTGTCTCTCTGATTCTGTTCAAACACAAAGAAGAAGAA
 CAAGAATGGATACATCATTCCATTAGTAGTCGTAGGAATCATCGTCTGTTCTTTTACGGCTTTAGCTTTG
 TTCCGGCGTTTCAAGAAAAACAACAAGAGGTACACTTGGTGAAGGAAATGGGCCGTTGAAAACCTGCA
 AAGCGATACTTTAAGTACTCAGAAGTTGTGAATATCACAATAACTTTGAGAGAGTTATTGGCAAAGGAG
 GTTTTGGTAAAGTATACCATGGTGTCAATAATGGAGAACAAGTTGCTGTCAAGGTAAGTCTCTGAAGAATC
 AGCTCAAGGCTACAAAGAGTTTCGAGCAGAGGTTGACCTTCTCATGAGAGTTCATCACACGAACCTGAC

TTCTCTTGTTGGATATTGCAACGAAATAAACCACATGGTGCTTATCTATGAGTATATGGCTAATGAGA
 TAGGAGACTATTTGGCAGGTAAAAGGTCATTTATCTTGAGCTGGGAAGAGAGGTTGAAGATATCATTAG
 ATGCAGCGCAAGGACTAGAGTATCTTCACAATGGTTGTAAGCCTCTATAGTTACAGAGATGTGAAGC
 CAACAAACATCTTACTAAACGAGAAGCTCCAAGCGAAGATGGCGGACTTCGGGTTATCTAGAAGCTTCT
 CTGTTGAAGGAAGCGGTCAGATTTCAACAGTTGTGCTGGATCCATCGGTTACCTTGACCCCGAGTACT
 ATTCGACTCGCCAAATGAACGAAAAGAGTGATGTTTATAGTCTTGGGGTTGTTCTTCTTGAAGTGATTAC
 AGGCCAACCTGCTATTGCAAGCTCAAAAACAGAGAAGGTGCATATAAGTGATCATGTGAGGTCATATTA
 GCCAACGGAGACATTAGAGGAATCGTGGATCAGCGTCTAAGAGAGAGATGACGTTGGCTCGGCTTG
 GAAAATGTCAGAGATCGCTCTTGCTTGTACCGAGCACACTTCTGCGCAGAGGCCAACGATGAGTCAGG
 TCGTTATGGAGCTGAAACAGATTGTTTATGGCATAAGTACTGATCAGGAAAACACTACGATGACTCGACGA
 AAATGCTTACAGTGAATCTAGACACCGAGATGGTTCCTCGAGCAAGGTAG

Supplement figure S1B: indicating the position of *At*FRK1 forward and reverse primer in the FRK1 nucleotide sequence

Arabidopsis thaliana nucleotide sequence of PP2A (AT1G13320)

ATGTCTATGGTTGATGAGCCTTTATACCCGATTGCTGTGCTTATCGACGAGCTAAAAACGATGATATTC
 AGCGTAGATTGAACTCTATTAACCGCTTTCTATCATTGCTCGTCTTGGAGAGGAGAGGACAAGAA
 AAGAGTTGATTCCATTTCTTAGTGAGAA CAATGACGATGACGATGAGGTGCTTTGGCTATGGCGGAAG
 AGTTGGGGGGTTTTATTCTGTATGTAGGAGGGGTTGAGTATGCATATGTTCTGCTTCCACCTTTGGAGA
 CTCTATCCACTGTTGAGGAACTTGCCTGAGGGGAGAAAGCTGTGGATTCACTTTGTAGAATTGGTGCTC
 AGATGAGGGAGAGTACTTGGTTGAGCATTTCACTCCTCTGGCTAAGCGACTTTCAGCTGGTGAATGGT
 TCACAGCCAGAGTATCAGCATGTGGGATTTCCATATTGCATACCCAAGTGCCCCAGATGTGCTAAAGA
 CGGAGCTAAGATCAATATATGGTCAGCTTTGTCAAGATGACATGCCAATGGTGCGCAGAGCTGCAGCAA
 CTAATTTGGGGAAGTTTGTCTACAATTGAATCAGCTCATTTGAAGACAGACATTATGTCCATGTTTGA
 GGATCTTACGCAAGATGATCAAGATTCGGTTAGATTATTGGCTGTTGAGGGTTGTGCTGCTCTTGGGAA
 ATTGTTGGAGCCCCAGGACTGTGTTGCACACATTCTTCTGTGATTGTCAATTTCTCGCAGGATAAGTCC
 TGGCGTGTGCTTATATGTTGCAAATCAGCTACTTGAACCTTGTGAAGCTGTAGGACCCGAGCCAACT
 AGGACGGATCTGGTGCATATGCTCCTACTTTGTGATAATGAGGCAGAAGTTCGGATAGCAGCT
 GCTGAAAAGTTACCAAGTTTTGTGCGATTTTAAACCCTGAACTCGCTATCCAGCACATTCTCCCTGTG
 TAAAGGAATTATCATCAGACTCTTCTCAGCACGTCAGATCTGCATTGGCATCAGTTATAATGGGAATGGC
 TCCAGTCTTGGGTAAGATGCAACAATTGAGCATCTTCTTCCAATCTTTCTTCTATTGAAAGACGAATT
 TCCTGATGTACGCTTAAACATTATCAGCAAACCTTGACCAAGTGAACCAGGTTATTGGGATTGATCTACTA
 TCACAATCGTTACTGCCAGCCATTGTAGAATTTGCTGAAGACAGGCACTGGAGAGTACGTCTGGCTATA
 ATCGAGTATATCCCTTGTGGCCAGTCAATTAGGTGTAGGCTTCTTTGATGAGAAGCTTGGTGCTCTTT
 GCATGCAATGGTTACAAGACAAGGTTCACTCAATCCGTGAAGCTGCTGCAACAATCTGAAGCGTCTTG
 CTGAAGAGTTTGGTCTGAATGGGCAATGCAGCATATAGTTCTCAGGTTCTAGAGATGATTAACAACC
 CACTATCTATATCGGATGACGATTCTTCTGTCAGTATCGCTTCTCGCTCCAGTAATGGGATCCGAGAT
 CACATGTTCCAAACTCTTACCTGCGGTAATAACTGCATCTAAAGACAGAGTTCCAAACATCAAATTTAAC
 GTGGCCAAAATGATGCAATCTCTCATTCCGATAGTCGACCAAGCGGTTGTGGAGAACATGATACGGCCA
 TGCTTGGTGGAGCTAAGTGAAGACCCAGATGTTGATGTTCCGGTATTTGCAAAATCAAGCTCTCCAATCTA
 TTGACAATGTGATGATGTCTAGCTAA

Supplement figure S1C: indicating the position of *At*PP2A forward and reverse primer in the PP2A nucleotide sequence

Zea mays nucleotide sequence of C2 copy (4:192758391-192761788)

TCGTGTGACACTGTACGTGATCTATTAACCTGTAATTTTTTTTTGAAGTCATAAATAATAATTAATCTGAAA
 CAGTGAAAGTTATTTATCACAAAGTATCTGCCGCTAGCTCAACAACTAGTGAGAACACATCACTCGTGC
 GTCGTCGTTAATGCGTAGCAATAGGCAATAGCAATGTGTGCTACGTATTCTCTAGGAAAGTAAGTAGAAA
 CTACTACTAGTACTACTGTGTAGGCATGAGTTAAACACATGGAGGCATGATTTAAACACATGCAATGCAT
 TCACTGCCGCGAGAAGGAAAAAATGTAGAGAGAGGGGGGGGGTGTGATTCTACAAAACGACCAATC
 CTAAGAATCATCGATCGACTGTTTTACGTCAAGCGGAATACCTTTTAGACGTGCATGCAAGTGGCATAGA
 TCGATGACCTACCTTTCAAACCGTGTGTTTGTTCACATATCCAGGAAAATATAATACGTGTGCGCTAGAG
 CTAGCTATATATCTAGTCTACGTATAGTTGCGGGTAACGGTTTTCCGGTCTTTTTATTAATTTACCAC
 GGACGACGGAGACGACGATATTGTTGAATTTGGGCAGGCTGCAGGGCCGCCGACGACGGACGGA
 GCGTGAATTTCTGTGCGGCACACACGGCCGTGGTAGCTGACCGGACGACGACGAGACCGGTCGACCG

CATGTAGTGCAGGTGGGCGTGCCTGATGAGGGAGACGCTGACTCTGACTGGCTGCTGCTGGGTGTGC
AAGCATACCACTACTACTAGTACACCACACCAGGCTTGCCGCCCGCCCGCCCGCGGCCACGCGACCC
AACTAACCCCGGCGCGGGCGTTCCAGTGGGCGGGTCTCGATCCCCGGCAGTCCGCCCCGCGCG
TCGTCGCCGCCACGTGGCGGCCATCCGCCCGTCCAAGTACCTAACCCGGTCCGACGCCCGCGCG
CTTATATAAACGCCCCACCGGCTTCCGTCTCTCCCACACCACAGCTCCCACACACAGCAGGCAGCA
GCTCGATCGCTAGCTCCTCCGAACCGGAAAGCCAAGCCCGCTTTGGCGATCGTGTCTTGTCTTGGT
TCCTTCAATTCTGCCGGAGCCAGCGAGAGCTAGCTGCTGCTGTCGCGTGTAGACGTCGTCTTGCCA
GCGAGAGCCTAGCTCGATCGGTCTCTCTGGTACAACGTAGGGAGAAAGATCGAGGGGAGAGGACGA
CGACGATGGCCGGCGGACCCGTGACCCGTGGAGGAGGTGAGGAAGGCCAGCGCGCCACCGGCCCG
CCACCGTGCTGGCGATCGGCACCGCCACGCCCGCCAAGTGCCTGTACCAGGCCGACTACCCGGACTA
CTACTTCCGGATCACCAAGAGCGAGCACCTCACCGACCTCAAGGAGAAATTCAAGAGGATGTGTGAGT
GCCCCGCCCTCGATTATATATCTAGCTCACTCTCTCTCGCCCCGTCTCCATCCCTCGCTCGCTCGTAGC
TTGAAGAACATACTACACTCACGTCACGTCGTCGTCGTCCTGCTACCTGCTTAATTGTTTCACGTCGTCGG
TAGGTCTCGGGCGACGACTACTAGCTGACGACGGACGATGCTAGCTAGCTGCTGCCTCGTGCGCAGCA
GCTTCCACGTATTAATTTTCTCCGTCCCCTCGCGCCATGCACAAAGACATGAATATTTTACTAACCCAC
GTAGTCTATTGTCTCTCTGGGTAACACTCGTGGGTAGTACTATCTAGCTACTACTTATCTGAATATT
TTTACTAGCAGTGGGAGAACAGAAAGCTAATAGACTACGGTCGATCGTACGTGTCGTCCTCTTCGTTTAA
TTTTAACAGATTCCAAAACTTCTCCATCATATGAATATATACTCTATGTTGCGATCCGGATAGAGAGA
GAATATAACTGCAATAAACTCCTTGTGTTGAGATATGTATATGCTGCTTGTGCTACACAATTGCTACTA
CCTAGGCAGTCGTACGTTACAACAACAACAACAGCAGCAAACTTGTGTGTGCACCATGAAACCCCG
TGTTCCATGATTTTTGGGGGCGCAGGTTAGCATGGACACTAGCTAGGCTAGGCTAGGATATGTTTTGG
GTAGGGTCCATATATATATACCAGCTGCTAACGAGCGAGTAACACACACGTACGCACGCACGCACGCAT
TCTAGCTCGGCCGATACCGTACAGACATGAAAAAAGAAGGTGCGTGGTCAACGCCCGCTGGCCGTG
CCCGTACCAACAACACTAACACAAACGTTTTTCATTTTCTTGGGGTGAAGAGAGAGAAAGTGAGAAC
GAGACGTAAGCAGGCGTCTGTGCACGGGAGTGAAGAGATAATACAGCTTTTTGTGCCCTGTACGGG
CTGTTAGGTGTGCAACACAAATGGCACGTCGAGGCGTCTTTTGGCCCGGCCCTCTGCTAGTTCTTCCAT
CACTGTTGCACACTGACCACTCAAGAAACCCGCTCTAATTAAGCTGTTGACCTCTTCTTCTTCTAGC
GCGCGTAGCTGATGAGTAGCTAGCGCACCAGAGTCCAGAGGTGGTAGCAGTAGAAACAGGATTCTTT
TCGTGGACGTCGATGTGCCATGCTAGCTGCCATCGTCCCACACTGCACGGGGCAGACAGGGACCCCGT
GCCGCCCACACTCGACTCACTACCTCAGGCTGCAGCTGACGCAACTCGTATAGAGAGATGGAATAGTA
CTCCATCAGCAGGCACTCCACACCACTTGGATTTTGCAGACTGACCGGCAAGCAACTAACCCCTTC
CTGTTCCATCAATCGAATTGACGTAGCAACTAGCTGCCTTGACGTCCGTGCTCGGGCATGGCCAGTACA
CATACGGCCGCGCGGTACGGTTTTGTTTTAATTGGGCCGTTTTGATTTTACGTGCATGCAGGCGACAA
GTCGATGATCCGGAAGCGTTACATGCACCTGACGGAGGAGTTCCTGGCGGAGAACCAGCATGTGC
GCGTACATGGCGCCGTCGCTGGACGCGCGGCAGGACGTGGTGGTGGTGGAGGTGCCGAAGCTGGGG
AAGGCGGCGGCGCAGAAGGCGATCAAGGAGTGGGGGCGCCAAAGTCGCGGATCACGCACCTGGTG
TTCTGCACCACGTCCGGGGTGGACATGCCGGGCGCCGACTACCAGCTGACCAAGGCGCTGGGCCTGC
GCCCCCTCCGTGAACCGCCTCATGATGTACCAGCAGGGGTGCTTCGCGGGCGGCACGGTGTGCGCGT
GGCCAAGGACCTCGCGGAGAACAACCGCGGCGCGCGGGTGTGGTGGTGTGCTCCGAGATCACGGC
CGTCACGTTCCGCGGCCCTCCGAGTCGCACCTCGACTCGCTCGTGGGCCAGGCGCTGTTCCGGCGAC
GGCGCGGCGGCCGTGGTGTGGGCGCCGACCCGGACCGCGTTCGAGCGCCCGCTCTCCAGCTC
GTCTCCGCCGCCAGACCATCCTGCCGACTCGGAGGGCGCCATCGACGGCCACCTCCGCGAGGTGG
GGCTCACCTTCCACCTGCTCAAGGACGTGCCTGGCCTCATCTCCAAGAACATCGGCCGCGCGCTGGAC
GACGCGTTCAAGCCGCTCGGCATCTCCGACTGGAACCTCATCTTCTGGGTGGCGCACCCCGGCCGGC
CCGCCATCCTCGACCAGGTGGAGGCCAAGGTCCGGGCTGGACAAGGCCAGGATGCGCGCCACCCGCC
ACGTCTCTCCGAGTACGGCAACATGTCCAGCGCCTGCGTCTCTTTCATCCTCGACGAGATGCGCAAG
CGCTCCGCCGAGGACGGACAGGCCACCACGGGCGAGGGCCTCGACTGGGGCGTCTCTTCCGGCTTC
GGCCCGGACTCACCGTCGAGACCGTCTGTGCTCCACAGCGTCCCCATCACACCCGGAGCGGCCACCG
CCTGATTCATCGATTCAACGATCAAATTCCTCCCCTCTCCGATCCAATTCGTCGTCGTCGTTCTGT
CATTATTTTACGTCGTCGTCGCAATAATGTGCTCTCTGCTATAATTGTCGTGTGTAGTAGTAAGTAG
CTGTTACTATTTTCCATGTAAGTGTGAGGAGAAGACCCCTTATCGTTGTCACCTTTAGCATGCATGGG
GTGGTGAGGTATTGGGTATACCTGTGTAAGACAAGCTTGGCTGGTTTAAATTATATATTTTTTTTTAAAAA
AATCTGTTTATACAAAAATAACACCTGTAATGTGCATGGTGCAGGCCAAATTGACCGCCATTTTCAGTGC
ACCTAAAGCTGTATTGGAT

Supplement figure S2A: indicating the position of *ZmC2* forward and reverse primer in the C2 nucleotide sequence

Zea mays nucleotide sequence of WHP1 copy (2:224558005-224561990)

TTGTGATGTTTGCAGATATGTGAGATCTATGATGTATGTGATGGTTCTATGATGTTTGCAGATATGATGT
ATGTGATATTTGTGAAGTACATGAGGTGTTGATATATCTTTTGTGGTTGTTGGACGGAATATAAAAAACAA
ATAAAAAGCGGGTATGTGGACACTTTGCCGAGTGTTCGACTCGGCAAAGGTACAACCAAGGTAGAAT
AGCTGGTAACCGGGAAATTATCTTTGTGAGTGTATGTCTAAGGTAAGTACTCGGCAAAGGCTCCACGTTTGC
CGAGTGATATGTCTCAGGTAAGTACTCGGCAGACGTGCAATCTTTTGCAGTGTTCAGCAACTGGCACTCG
GCAAAGGATCAACCTCTGTGAGTGTGCATACGGCGCACTCGGTATAGAAACTATGCAGGGAGGCGCCGT
CGGAGGTTTTTGCAGAGTGCCTCAGACCCAGGCAAAGGCTCTGTACAGTACCCGCTGCCCTCAC
GACGACTTTACTTTACCGAGTGGCCAATTGCAAGTACCCGACAAACAAGCCGTTGTACCCGATGACCAC
CGTTTTAACGAGCCTTCTTTGTGAGTGCCTGCTTTTCGAGCCTTTGCAGAACTCGGCAAATAAGCCGTG
TCCAGTAGTGTAAGGGAGACAAGGGCAAAAAAAGAGGGTAATACAGAATGTAGAAGTGGTGTGGA
CGTGTCTTTTGTGGTTGGATCCCCATAATCCTGCGAGCAATTATATTGTCGTGCAGCTGCAGCTAGCCT
GCAGTGCATCGATGAATCAACAACACGTAAGTGTAAAGTACATGTTCCCTAAATCGTAACGGG
TGGCATTATCCTGAACACAAGAGGGCCGACGTACGGTTGTAATAAATACTACATTACTACTACGG
AAAAAGTTGGTTTGCAGTACGTGGGTTTTACCACCGAGAGACGATTATTGTTGAAACGAAGCCGTG
GTAGCTGACCAGGTGACGACGCGAGAACGAGCGAGAAGTACCCATACCCACGCGACCCAACTAACTAC
TAAAGCACCCCGTGGCGGCCCTTGCGCCCGTCCAACCTACCTAACCCGACCGCGCGGCTATATAAGCA
CCGCACCCCGGCGGGCCTCCTCTGCCATTAAGACTAGCTAACTAGCGTGAAGAGCTCCTCCGACGAC
TACTAGCTCTCGTTGCTCCGACGACCCCTGCCGGCCGCTCTGGTACAACGTACGAGAGGAAGAGAG
ACGATCGATGGCCGGCGCCACCGTGACCGTGGACGAGGTGAGGAAGGGCCAGCGCGGACCCGGCC
CGCCACCGTGCTGGCCATCGGGACGGCGACGCCCGCCAACCTGCGTGTACCAGGCCGACTACCCGGAC
TACTACTTCCGGATCACCAGAGCGACCCCTACCCGACCTCAAGGAGAAGTTCAAGAGGATGTGTGA
GTATCTCTACTACCCCTACCCCTACCCCTACCCCTACCTACTATCGTCCGCTCCACGCTCGCTCTACGCATCAA
ACCGCAAGAGCTTGCCTCGTTGAGCAGCTCGTGCATCGTGCCTCCACACACCCGCTCTCCCGCTCG
CTCTCTTGTCTTCTTCTCGTGCAGCAGTACGACGATCGACCCACGACGATGCTGCATGGCGTTATAACGTCGTA
AGACTCTATAGCTTGACAATGACGACCCCGTACAGTACTGCAGTGGAGATCGAGCGATGCATGACTAC
GGTCTCGCTCGTCTTGTCTTCAAATTCGCACTTATTATTGCACCACTAGTCTTCTTCTACTCTGTTG
ACGACGACAGAAGCAGACATGCATGCATGCATGCACTCACGCGAGCCAAATATTTAATCCTTAATCAGC
TAGGACCACATGTCCAGGTAGAGAAGAATTAGCTAGAGAGATTGCCCGGGTACGGTAGCAAATTAAC
CACGCACGCACTAGAATTAGCCAACAACGTTTTGTTAGCTAGGGCACATGCAGTACGTACAACCTATA
TTATATAAATTACTCGTATCTTAATTAAGTGGTGTGTTGAAGGAGACAAGTGAAGAAAAAACACGACGTA
GCACACTAGCATGGTTCTAATATACGATTTTCATCCATACAACCCAGTAAATGAGACATGTCTTAAGTGT
TCTAGTGAATTAATATATAAGATACAAGGCTCAGCACTGGTACAGAGAAGCTCTATACAGTCCGTTCTGA
ACACATTTGCATTAGCGTTTTTCAGATCCGCTAGTTCTACGGGCCAGTAGAAAAAATTGTACAAATTC
GTGGCTCCGTTGAAGTCGCAAGTCTGATATTTTTCGCGGAAAATTGCGGGCCGGTTGGAATCTAACC
ACAAAAAACCCTCCCTCACGCGAAGCCTCCTCTACCACTTACCTATATGACGTGCCTTGTATCTATAT
TGCAGTTTTGTTGCCACGTAGAACAATTCGAGTATAAATTGACTACTTGAGGCTATGAACGAATCCAA
ACGAAAAAAGTTGTTAACTACAAAGTTTCGTAACTTTTGAAGTTATATAACTTTTATCTTGATACCTTTCTT
TCCATGCGAGGTCGTTTGCAAAATTTGCATTTTGCATTTGACAAAATTCGAATGCATTTTTTGGAGACGA
GATGATTTCAAATAAAAAAAGTTTTCAATTATAAAGTTCCATAACTTTTGAAGATCTACAAATTTTTATGTT
GGTGGTTTTACCATCCGATGTCGTTTGA AAAACTAAAAAATTAAGGATGAAAATGTTTTCTAGTGGCTG
TTTTTTTTAAAAAATTGCCACTACAAATAGTACTGGCGGTTGATAATCAAATTCATTTGCAAAAAATCAA
ATCCACCCGCGTGTCTTGAACCTTTTTCTGCTAGTGTAGATACCTTAGACTATATGTGATATATAACCATG
AACTGGATACGTGACACAAAACAGCACAAACTTTGTGTGCACCACACATGCATAAAAACCCCGTGTTCCT
GGAATTCGGGGGCCATCGACGAGCACGCGACAAGCGTGCAATTCTAGCTAGCTAGCTAGCCCAA
TACCGGCCGTACGGAGTTCATGGGAATGTGATGAAGTGGAGGAGGGTCAACAACGGCCGTGCGTGCA
TGCCGGCGACAGCACACGTACGGATCATCTTGAATAATAACAAAAAAGTGAAGTTGAATAATAACAG
ACTGTTAGTAGCAAGCATGGTAATAATAAGTCAAGGCGCGTCTACTAGTTGCTAGCTACTCCTAGCT
AGTTGACGGCCTGCTGCTGATCCAACCTTCCAAAAAATTAATAAATCAGGCCTTGTAACTCTCTT
GGTACTAGTAACAAACAATCTTAGAAATCTAATCAAATTTAATGCCGGAGGAGACAACTGGTGTACT
ACTTATTTGCTTCTTTTGTGGACGGCGACGGGCCGGCCGGCCTACGTGCTATATACTACGCGTACTT
GCATGCTTGTAGCCCAAGAATATGTTGGGCTCAGGGCCACAGGGCAGACAGCAACGGCATGCCGGC
CGATCCGCCATCGTCAAGGCAACGGTGTCTCCTAGCTAATTCATTGCATGGCATGGCCATGGCATCCG
TGCAGGCGACAAGTGCATGATCCGGAAGCGGTACATGCACCTGACGGAGGAGTTCTGTCTGCGGAGA
CCGAGCATGTGCGCGTACATGGCGCCGTGCTGACGCGCGGACAGGACGTTGGTGTGACGGAGGTG
CCGAAGCTGGGAAGGCGGCGCGCAGAAGGCGATCAAGGAGTGGGGGCAGCCAAAGTCGCGGATC
ACGCACCTGGTGTCTGCACCACGTGCGGGGTGGACATGCCGGGCGCCGACTACCAGCTGACCAAGG
CGCTGGGGCTGCGCCGTCCGTGAACCGCCTGATGATGTACCAGCAGGGGTGCTTCGCGGGCGGCAC
GGTGTGCGCGTGGCCAAGGACCTGGCGGAGAACAACCGCGGGGCGAGGGTCTGGTGGTGTGCTC
GGAGATCACGGCCGTGACGTTCCGCGGGCCGTCCGAGTCGCACCTGGACTCGCTCGTGGGGCAGGC
GCTGTTCCGGCAGCGCGCGGCGGCCGTGCTGGTGGGCGCCGACCCGGACGGGCGGGTTCGAGCGCC
CGCTGTTCCAGCTCGTGTGCGCGGCGCAGACCATCCTGCCGACTCGGAGGGCGCCATCGACGGCCA
CCTCCGCGAGGTGGGGCTGACGTTCCACCTGCTCAAGGACGTTGCCCGGGCTCATCTCCAAGAATC
GAGCGCGCGCTGGAGGACGCGTTCGAGCCGCTCGGCATCTCCGACTGGAACCTCATCTTCTGGGTG

CGCACCCCGGCGGGCCCGCCATCCTGGACCAGGTGGAGGCCAGGGTCGGGCTGGACAAGGCCAGGA
 TGCGCGCCACCCGCCACGTCCTCTCCGAGTACGGCAACATGTCCAGCGCCTGCGTGCTCTTCATCCTG
 GACGAGATGCGCAAGCGCTCCGCCGAGGACGGCCAGGCCACCACCGGCGAGGGGCTCGACTGGGGC
 GTCCTCTTCGGCTTCGGCCCCGGGCCTCACCGTCGAGACCGTCGTGCTCCACAGCGTCCCCATCACCAC
 CGGAGCGCCACCGCCGCCTGAGTCGTCCATCTATCCTCGCGATCGCTCCAGACATGAACGACCCGAC
 CTACGAATAATGTATCTGCGTAATTAATTACTATCTGTCTTGTGTCTAGTAGTGTAAAAACCCCTAA
 TTAATTTTATTATGGGCGAGCTAGCTCAAGAGTGGAGTCATAAAAACCGCATGGATGGTGAGGTATTGTAT
 AGTACCTGTGTAAGACAAGCTTGGCTGGTTTTTTTTATTTTATATTTTAAATCTGTTTGCTCAAGACAAAACA
 AAAAAAAAAAATGAATTGTTGAGCTGTCATTAATTTGCAGTGCACCAGCTCAAGTTGGTTGTACTCCTATC
 CTATGTATGAAATGAAATCCCTTCTAGTAGTATCTAAAAAGGAATTGTAGTAGGCTGTCGTTTTCCAGTG
 CGTGCACCTCAATAGTGAG

Supplement figure S2B: indicating the position of *ZmWHP1* forward and reverse primer in the WHP1 nucleotide sequence

Zea mays nucleotide sequence of house-keeping gene PP2A

ATGATTAAGCAGATCCTTGGCAGGCTGCCGAGGAAGCCGGGGAAGGCTGGGGATAGCCGGGAAGCTG
 CTGCTGCGGGGAATGGAAGTGAAGCCGTGCAATTCCTACAGTGTTGCGAGGAGCATGGACCCAGGTAAC
 AAAAGGGCTGGAAATGGAGATTACCCAGTTCCATCTGGTGTAAATCCGAATCCAGTGATGAATGGGGCT
 GTGGTGTATCACTCCAATGAACCCTTACCGGCATTCAAGGACGTGCCCATGTCAGAGAAGCAGAATTTG
 TTTGTCAAGAAGGTGAGCCTATGTTGCGCTGTGTATGACTTTGTGGATCCAATAAGAACCTCAAGGAG
 AAGGAGGTGAAGCGCCAGACACTTATGGAGCTTGTGATTACGTCGCTTCCGCTAATGGCAAGTTCTCT
 GAGGTTGTCATGCTGGAGATCACAAAGATGGTGTCAATTAATTTGTTCCGGAGCTCCAGCCCCACACCT
 CGTGAGAACAAGCCATTGAAGGGGTCGATCTGGAGGAGGATGAGCCTCTCATGGATCCTGCATGGTC
 TCACCTACAGATCGTGTACGAGGTTTTCTTGAGATTTGTAGCTTCACAGGAGACAGATGCAAAGTTGGC
 CAAGAGATATATAGACCATTCCCTTATCCTTAGGCTGCTAGACCTTTTTGACTCTGAGGACCCCAGGGAA
 AGGGACTATCTAAAGACGATACTTCATCGAATATATGGTAAATTCATGGTCCATCGACCATTTCATCAGGA
 AAGCAATTAACAACATATTCTACAGGTTTTATATTCGAAACAGAGAAACATAAATGGTGTTCAGAGTTGTT
 GGAGATCCTGGGCAGTATTATCAATGGGTTTGCCCTTCCACTTAAGGAAGAGCACAAATTGTTCTTGT
 CGTGCATGATCCCTCTTACAAGCCGAAATGTGTATCTATGTACCATCAGCAGCTATCGTATTGCATCA
 CACAGTTTGTGAGAAGGACTGCAAACCTTGGTACACAGTTATTAGGGGTTTACTTAAATATTGGCCTGT
 GACGAACAGTTCAAAGGAGGTGATGTTCTTGGGTGAGTTAGAGGAGTTTTAGAGGCAACACAGCTTG
 CAGAGTTCCAAAGATGCATGGTTCCACTCTTCCGTCAGATTAGCCGTAGCATGAACAGCTTTTCATTTCCA
 GGTGGCAGAGCGGGCTCTGTTTCTCTGGAACAATGACCATATTGAAACCCTAATTAAGCAAAACTACAA
 GGTGCTGTTACCGATCATCTATCCAGCACTCGAGAGAACTCCAGAGATCACTGGAACCAAGCTGTCCG
 TAGCCTGACACTGAACGTACGCAAGATCTTCTCAGACCATGATTCCACATTCTTCGGGGAGTGCGTCCA
 GAGGTTCAAGTACGAGGAGCTCAAGCAGGCGGAATCTGATTCAAACGAGACGCCATGTG**GAAGCGCC**
TGGAGGAAATGGGTGCCTCAAACCTGGCGGGAACCATCCCTTAGGTGCACC**CAATGGCAAACCCAGT**
CACGCTGCTGGCTAG

Supplement figure S2C: indicating the position of *ZmPP2A* forward and reverse primer in the PP2A nucleotide sequence

PREDICTED: LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase FLS2
 [Zea mays]

Sequence ID: ref|XP_008668880.1|Length: 1190Number of Matches: 1

Related Information

Gene-associated gene details

Map Viewer-aligned genomic context

Range 1: 45 to 1183GenPeptGraphics

Next Match

Previous Match

Alignment statistics for match #1	Score	Expect	Method	Identities
Positives		Gaps		
969 bits(2504)		0.0	Compositional matrix adjust.	526/1143(46%)
746/1143(65%)		20/1143(1%)		

Supplement Figures

Query	30	EIEALKSFKNGISNDPLGLVSDWTIIIGSL-----RHCNWTGITCDSTGHVVSLSLLE	81
		+EAL +FK ++ DP G L+ WT+ +HCNWTG+ CD GHV S+ L++	
Sbjct	45	HLEALLAFKKAVTADPNGLTTSWTVGSGGGGGGGRYPQHCNWTGVACDGAGHVTSIELVD	104
Query	82	KQLEGVLSPAIANLTYLQVLDLTSNSFTGKIPAEIGKLTENQLILYLNYFSGSIPSGIWI	141
		L G L+P + N++ LQ+LDLTSN F G IP ++G+L L L+L N +G+IP +	
Sbjct	105	TGLRGTLTPFLGNISTLQLLDLTSNRFGGGIPPQLGRLDGLEGLVLGANNLTGAIPPELG	164
Query	142	ELKNIFYLDRNLLSGDVPEEICKTSSLVLIGFDYNNLTGKIPECLGDLVHLQMFVAAG	201
		L ++ LDL NN L G +P +C S++ + N+LTG +P+C+GDL +L V +	
Sbjct	165	GLGSLQLLDSNNTLRGGIPRRLCNCSSAMAGLSVFNNDLTGAVPDCIGDLTNLNLVLSL	224
Query	202	NHLTGSIPVSIPTLANLTDLDLSDGNQLTGKIPRDFGNLLNLQSLVLTENLLEGDIPAEIG	261
		N L G +P S L L LDLSGNQ +G IP GN L + + EN G IP EIG	
Sbjct	225	NSLDGELPPSFARLTRLETLDLSDGNQFSGPIPPGGIGNFSRLNIVHMFENRFSGAIPPEIG	284
Query	262	NCSSLVQLELYDNQLTGKIPAEELGNLVQLQALRIYKNKLTSSIPSSFLRLTQLTHLGLSE	321
		C +L L +Y N+LTG IP+ELG L L+ L +Y N L+S IP SL R L L LS	
Sbjct	285	RCKNLTTLNVYSNRLTGAIPSELGELASLKVLLLYGNALSSEIPRSLGRCASLVSLQLSM	344
Query	322	NHLVGPISSEIIGFLESLEVLTLHSNNFTGEFPQSITNLRNLTVLTGVFNNSIGELPADLG	381
		N L G I E+G L SL L LH+N TGE P S+ +L NLT L+ +N+++SG LPA++G	
Sbjct	345	NQLTGSIPAEELGELRSLRKLMLHANRLTGEVPASLMDLVNLTYSFSYNSLSGPLPANIG	404
Query	382	LLTNLRNLSAHDNLLTGPISSISNCTGLKLLDLSHNQMTGEIPRGFGRM-NLTFISIGR	440
		L NL+ L +N L+GPIP+SI+NCT L + N+ +G +P G G++ NL F+S+	
Sbjct	405	SLQNLQVLIQNNLSLGPPIASIANCTSLYNASMGFNEFSGPLPAGLQQLNLHFLSLAD	464
Query	441	N-HFTGEIPDDIFNCSNLETLSVADNNTGTLKPLIGKLQKLRILQVSYNSLTGPIPREI	499
		N +G+IP+D+F+CSNL TL++A N+ TG+L P +G+L +L +LQ+ N+L+G IP E+	
Sbjct	465	NDKLSGDIPEDLFDLCSNLRTLTLAGNSFTGSLSPRVGRLESELQQLQGNALSGAIPPEEM	524
Query	500	GNLKDLNILYLHNSNGFTGRIPREMSNLTLLQGLRMYSDLEGPIPEEMFDMKLLSVLDS	559
		GNL L L L NGF GR+P+ +SNL+ LQ L + N L+G +P+E+F ++ L+VL ++	
Sbjct	525	GNLTKLIALQLGGNGFVGRVPKSISNLSSLQKLTQQLQNRDLGALPDEIFGLRQLTVLSVA	584
Query	560	NNKFSGQIPALFSKLESITYLSLQGNKFNQSI PASLKSLSLLNTFDISDNLTTGTIPGEL	619
		+N+F G IP S L SL++L + N NG++PA++ SL L T D+S N L G IP L	
Sbjct	585	SNRFVGPIDAVSNLRSLSFLDMSNNALNGTVPAAVGSLDHLTLDLNLRLAGAIPPSAL	644
Query	620	LASLKNMQLYLNFSSNNLLTGTIPKELGKLEMVQEIIDLSSNNLFSGSI PRSLQACKNVFTLD	679
		+A L +Q+YLN SNN TG IP E+G L MVQ IDLSNN SG +P +L CKN+++LD	
Sbjct	645	IAKLSALQMYLNLNSNGFTGPIPTTEIGALTMVQSIDLSNNRSLGGVPSTLAGCKNLYSLD	704
Query	680	FSQNNLSGHIPDEVFQGMDMIISLNLRSNFSGEIPQSFGNMTHLVSLDLSSNNLTGEIP	739
		S NNL+G +P +F +D++ SLN+S N G+IP + G + ++ +LD S N TG +P	
Sbjct	705	LSANNLTGALPAGLPHLDVLTSLNISGNELDGDIPSNIGALKNIQTLDASRNAFTGALP	764
Query	740	ESLANLSTLKHKLKASNNLKGHPESGVFKNINASDLMGNTDLCGSKKPLKPKCTIKQKSS	799
		+LANL++L+ L L+ N +G VP+SGVF N++ S L GN LCG K L PC K	
Sbjct	765	SALANLTSRSLNLSWNQFEGPVPDSGVFSNLSMSSLQGNAGLCGWKL-LAPCRHGGKKG	823
Query	800	HFSKRTRVILIIILGSAALLLVLLLVLILTCCCKKEKKEIENSSESSLPDLDSALKLKRFE	859
		FS+ +L++L A LLL++L+ ++ ++ +KK ++ +S + +L++F	
Sbjct	824	-FSRTGLAVLVLLVLAVALLLLVLVLTILFLGYRRYKKGSTGANSFAEDFVVPPELRKFT	882
Query	860	PKELEQATDSFN SANIIGSSSLSTVYKQGL--EDGTVI AVKVLNLKEFSAESDKWIFYTEA	917
		EL+ AT SF+ N+IGSS+LSTVYKG L DG V+AVK LNL +F A+SDK F TE	
Sbjct	883	CSELDAAATSSFDEGNVIGSSNLSTVYKGVLEPDGKVVAVKRLNLAQFPAKSDKCFLTEL	942
Query	918	KTLSQLKHRNLVKILGFAWESGKTKALVLPFMENGNLEDTIHGSA--APIGSLLEKIDLC	975
		TLS+L+H+NL +++G+A E GK KA+VL FM+NG+L+ IHG A ++ E++ C	
Sbjct	943	ATLSRLRHKNLARVVGYACEPGKIKAVVLEFMDNGDLGAIHGPRDAQRWTVPERLRAC	1002

Supplement Figures

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Query 976 VHIASGIDYLSHSGYGFPIVHCDLKPANILLSDRVAHVSDFGTARILGFR--EDGSTTAS 1033
V +A G+ YLH+GY FPIVHCD+KP+N+LLSD A VSDFGTAR+LG + + +A+
Sbjct 1003 VSVAHGLAYLHTGYDFPIVHCDVKPSNVLLSDWEARVSDFGTARMLGVHLTDAAAQSAT 1062

Query 1034 TSAFEGTIGYLAPEFAYMRKVTTKADVFSFGIIMMELMTKQRPTSLNDEDSQDMTLRQLV 1093
+SAF GTIGY+APEFAYMR V+ K DVFSFG++MMEL TK+RPT + +E+ +TL+Q V
Sbjct 1063 SSAFRGTIGYMAPEFAYMRTVSAKVDVFSFGVLMMEFLT KRRPTGMIEEEGVPLTLQQYV 1122

Query 1094 EKSIGNGRKGMVRVLDMELGDSIVSLKQEEAIEDFLKLCLFCTSSRPEDRPDMNEILTHL 1153
+ +I G G++ VLD +L +V+ + D L L L C +S P DRPDM+ +L+ L
Sbjct 1123 DNAISRGLDGVLDVLDVDPDL--KVVTEGDLSTVADVLSLALSCAASDPADRPDMDSVLSAL 1180

Query 1154 MKL 1156
+K+
Sbjct 1181 LKM 1183
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Supplement figure S3: *Arabidopsis thaliana* FLS2 amino acid sequence comparison with the closest homolog of *Zea mays* obtained by NCBI BLAST

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Declaration

Herewith, I declare that this thesis has been completed independently and unaided and that no other sources other than the ones given here have been used. The submitted written version of this work is the same as the one electronically saved and submitted on CD. Furthermore, I declare that this work has never been submitted at any other time and anywhere else as a final thesis.

18.06.2019

Date, Signature